

**SCREENING OF NEXT GENERATION FUNGICIDES AGAINST
Alternaria brassicicola CAUSING ALTERNARIA BLIGHT OF
MUSTARD**

MS THESIS

MD. ATIKUR RAHMAN

**Department of Plant Pathology
Bangladesh Agricultural University
Mymensingh-2202**

JUNE 2018

**SCREENING OF NEXT GENERATION FUNGICIDES AGAINST
Alternaria brassicicola CAUSING ALTERNARIA BLIGHT OF
MUSTARD**

A Thesis

Submitted to

Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh

In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of

Master of Science

In

Plant Pathology

By

MD. ATIKUR RAHMAN

Roll No.: 16 P.Path JD 19 M

Registration No.: 38704

Session: 2011-2012

**Department of Plant Pathology
Bangladesh Agricultural University
Mymensingh**

JUNE 2018

**SCREENING OF NEXT GENERATION FUNGICIDES AGAINST
Alternaria brassicicola CAUSING ALTERNARIA BLIGHT OF
MUSTARD**

A Thesis

Submitted to

**Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh
In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of
Master of Science**

**In
Plant Pathology**

By

MD. ATIKUR RAHMAN

Approved as to style and content by

**(Prof. Dr. Muhammed Ali Hossain)
Supervisor**

**(Prof. Dr. M. Bahadur Meah)
Co-Supervisor**

**Prof. Dr. Muhammed Ali Hossain
Chairman, Examination Committee
&
Head, Department of Plant Pathology
Bangladesh Agricultural University
Mymensingh**

JUNE 2018

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

All praises are due to Almighty Allah, the creator of the universe and source of all knowledge who has enabled the author to complete this research work and submitting the thesis for the degree of Master of Science (MS) in Plant Pathology successfully.

*The author would like to express his deepest sense of appreciation, gratitude, and indebtedness to his respected supervisor **Dr. Muhammed Ali Hossain**, Head & Professor, Department of Plant Pathology, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh for his precious advice, constant support and guidelines during the study period. The author is also grateful to him for providing encouragements and suggestions in the preparation of the manuscript.*

*The author also articulates his deepest sense of gratitude to his Co-supervisor **Dr. M. Bahadur Meah**, Professor, Department of Plant Pathology, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh for his valuable advice, support, encouragement and valuable suggestion throughout the research work.*

The author expresses his special indebtedness and heartfelt gratitude to his honourable teacher of the Department of Plant Pathology, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh for their valuable advice and helpful suggestions to accomplish the research work as well as complete this thesis.

The author wishes to render his cordial thanks to the laboratory staffs of the Department of Plant Pathology, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh for their valuable co-operation and help during the period of the research work.

The author acknowledges with gratitude for the financial assistance given by 'Ministry of Science and Technology' through National Science and Technology (NST) fellowship scheme 2017-2018.

*The author must express his very profound gratitude to his very special friend **Zohura** for providing him with unflinching support and continuous encouragement throughout his years of study and through the process of researching and writing this thesis. This accomplishment would not have been possible without her.*

*The author also expresses his cordial thanks to younger brother and sisters **Imran, Shatabdi, Lima, Kotha** and special thanks to his elder brother **Mr. Mahbub** scientific officer of BINA, relatives and another well-wisher for his countless blessings, constant inspiration and encouragement during his study period.*

*The author cannot repay the debts of beloved and dearest mother and gratefully remembers his Brothers and sisters and also his Uncle **Mr. Giash Uddin**, field officer of agronomy dept. BAU for their blessings and encouragement for his higher study.*

And finally, last but by no means least, he recalls his deep sense of love to the departed soul of his father whose entire desire comes to a fruitful outcome to his life through this higher study. Thank you.

June, 2018

The Author
(Md. Atikur Rahman Mamun)

SCREENING OF NEXT GENERATION FUNGICIDES AGAINST *Alternaria brassicicola* CAUSING ALTERNARIA BLIGHT OF MUSTARD

16 P.Path JD 19 M

ABSTRACT

Alternaria leaf blight/black leaf spot caused by *Alternaria brassicicola* is an important disease of mustard. Bioassay of twelve chemical fungicide(s) was verified against *Alternaria brassicicola* *in vitro* following poison food technique at the Plant-Microbe Interaction Lab, Department of Plant Pathology, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh. Total inhibition (100%) of mycelial growth of *A. brassicicola* was obtained by Hexaconazol (Contaf 5EC), Iprodion (Rovral 50 WP) and Carbendazim (Autostin 50WP) containing fungicides at the lowest (0.0125%) concentration. Other fungicides were either partially effective or ineffective. Two fungicides viz. Contaf 5EC and Rovral 50 WP were selected based on their *in vitro* performance sprayed in the field onto foliage of mustard plants in four different concentrations (0.0125%, 0.025%, 0.05% and 0.1%) to evaluate the *Alternaria* leaf blight incidence and severity and some yield contributing parameters in treated and control plots. Among the used fungicides, Contaf 5EC @ 0.1% concentration showed the best performance in reducing disease incidence and severity as well as increasing the yield parameters such as number of pod per plant (61), pod length (4.9 cm), number of seed per siliqua (26.01) and thousand seed weight (3.81g) followed by Rovral 50 WP @ 0.1% in single and double sprayed plots compared to control and other fungicidal treatments.

LIST OF CONTENTS

CHAPTER	TITLE	PAGE NO.
	ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	i
	ABSTRACT	ii
	LIST OF CONTENTS	iii
	LIST OF TABLES	vi
	LIST OF FIGURES	vii-viii
1	INTRODUCTION	1-2
2	REVIEW OF LITERATURE	3-14
	2.1 Literatures on <i>Alternaria</i> leaf blight disease of mustard- rapeseed	3
	2.2 Literatures on <i>Alternaria brassicicola</i> and <i>A. brassicae</i> pathogens	5
	2.3 Effect of chemical fungicides in controlling <i>Alternaria</i> leaf blight disease	8
3	MATERIALS AND METHODS	15-26
	3.1 Laboratory experiment	15
	3.1.1 Experimental Site	15
	3.1.2 Experimental period	15
	3.1.3 Experimental design	15
	3.1.4 Collection, Isolation and identification of <i>Alternaria</i> <i>brassicicola</i> isolate	15
	3.1.5 Fungicides and their specification	16
	3.1.6 Preparation of Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium	17
	3.1.7 Preparation of PDA containing fungicides	18
	3.1.8 Inoculation of PDA plate with <i>A. brassicicola</i>	18
	3.1.9 Collection of data	19
	3.1.10 Data analysis	19

CHAPTER	TITLE	PAGE NO.
3.2	Field experiment	19
3.2.1	Experimental site	19
3.2.2	Experimental period	20
3.2.3	Crop and Variety	20
3.2.4	Preparation of experimental Field	20
3.2.5	Sowing of seed	20
3.2.6	Fertilizer application	20
3.2.7	Intercultural operation	21
3.2.8	Treatments	22
3.2.9	Preparation of spray fungicide solution	22
3.2.10	Application of fungicide solution	23
3.2.11	Assessment of disease incidence and severity	23
3.2.12	Harvesting of crop	25
3.2.13	Data collection for the yield contributing parameters	25
3.2.14	Data analysis	26
4	RESULTS	27-53
4.1	Laboratory Experiment	27
4.1.1	Isolation and identification of <i>Alternaria brassicicola</i>	27
4.1.2	Effect of different fungicides at 0.0125% concentration on radial mycelial growth of <i>Alternaria brassicicola</i> over control at 10 Days after Inoculation	27
4.1.3	Effect of different fungicides at 0.0125% on percent growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> at 10 DAI	29
4.1.4	Effect of different fungicides at 0.025% concentration on radial mycelial growth of <i>Alternaria brassicicola</i> over control at 10 Days after Inoculation	31

CHAPTER	TITLE	PAGE NO.
4.1.5	Effect of different fungicides at 0.025% on percent growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> at 10 DAI	33
4.1.6	Effect of different fungicides at 0.05% concentration on radial mycelial growth of <i>Alternaria brassicicola</i> over control at 10 Days after Inoculation	35
4.1.7	Effect of different fungicides at 0.05% on percent growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> at 10 DAI	37
4.1.8	Effect of different fungicides at 0.1% concentration on radial mycelial growth of <i>Alternaria brassicicola</i> over control at 10 Days after Inoculation	39
4.1.9	Effect of different fungicides at 0.1% on percent growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> at 10 DAI	41
4.1.10	Effect of different fungicides at 0.2% concentration on radial mycelial growth of <i>A. brassicicola</i> over control at 10 Days after Inoculation	43
4.1.11	Effect of different fungicides at 0.2% on percent growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> at 10 DAI	45
4.2	Field experiment	47
4.2.1	Effect of fungicides on the disease incidence and severity of <i>Alternaria</i> leaf blight of mustard-rapeseed	47
4.2.1.1	Incidence and severity of <i>Alternaria</i> leaf blight disease of mustard in single sprayed plots	47
4.2.1.2	Incidence and severity of <i>Alternaria</i> leaf blight disease of mustard in double sprayed plots	50
4.2.2	Effect of foliar spray of fungicides on the yield contributing parameters of mustard	52
5	DISCUSSION	53-56
6	SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION	57-59
	REFERENCES	60-65

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE NO	TITLE	PAGE NO.
1	List of Fungicides along with their active ingredients used in this study	16
2	Disease severity scale (King, 1994)	24
3	Percent mycelial growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.0125% of different fungicide(s) separately over control	28
4	Percent mycelial growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.0125% of different fungicide(s) separately over control	30
5	Percent mycelial growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.025% of different fungicide(s) separately over control	32
6	Percent mycelial growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.025% of different fungicide(s) separately over control	34
7	Percent mycelial growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.05% of different fungicide(s) separately over control	36
8	Percent mycelial growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.05% of different fungicide(s) separately over control	38
9	Percent mycelial growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.1% of different fungicide(s) separately over control.	40
10	Percent mycelial growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.1% of different fungicide(s) separately over control.	42
11	Percent mycelial growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.2% of different fungicide(s) separately over control	44
12	Percent mycelial growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.2% of different fungicide(s) separately over control	46
13	Effect of fungicides on disease incidence and severity of Alternaria Leaf blight of mustard in Single Spray Plots	49
14	Effect of fungicides on disease incidence and severity of Alternaria Leaf blight of mustard in Double Spray Plots	51
15	Effect of different treatments on number of pods per plant, pod length, number of seeds per pod and thousand seeds weight of mustard at single and double spray plots	53

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE NO	TITLE	PAGE NO.
1	Different Field Activities (Weeding, Observation, Data Collections) are done by Researcher	21
2	Scale for assessing disease severity for <i>Alternaria</i> leaf blight of mustard (King, 1994)	24
3	Pure culture of <i>Alternaria brassicicola</i> (A) and different structures of <i>Alternaria brassicicola</i> (B)	27
4	Status of radial mycelial growth of <i>Alternaria brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.0125% of different fungicide(s) separately over control at 10 DAI (Days After Inoculation)	29
5	Growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates, here, Control and containing 0.0125% of A) Fiesta , B) Blitox, C) Endofil, D) Metaril, E) Cabrio, F) Bounty, G) Awal, H) Companion, I) Eminent, J) Autostin, K) Rovral and L) Contaf	31
6	Status of radial mycelial growth of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.025% of different fungicide(s) separately over control at 10 DAI (Days After Inoculation)	33
7	Growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates, here, Control and containing 0.025% of A) Fiesta, B) Blitox, C) Endofil, D)Metaril, E) Cabrio, F) Bounty, G) Awal, H) Companion, I) Eminent, J) Autostin, K) Rovral and L) Contaf	35
8	Status of radial mycelial growth of <i>Alternaria brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.05% of different fungicide(s) separately over control at 10 DAI (Days After Inoculation)	37
9	Growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates, here, Control and containing 0.05% of A) Blitox, B) Fiesta, C) Metaril, D) Bounty, E) Endofil, F) Cabrio, G) Awal, H) Companion, I) Eminent, J) Autostin, K) Rovral and L) Contaf	39
10	Status of radial mycelial growth of <i>Alternaria brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.1% of different fungicide(s) separately over control at 10 DAI (Days After Inoculation)	41

FIGURE NO	TITLE	PAGE NO.
11	Growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates, here, Control and containing 0.1% of A) Blitox, B) Fiesta, C) Metaril, D) Bounty, E) Endofil, F) Cabrio, G) Awal, H) Companion, I) Eminent, J) Autostin, K) Rovral and L) Contaf	43
12	Status of radial mycelial growth of <i>Alternaria brassicicola</i> on PDA plates containing 0.2% of different fungicide(s) separately over control at 10 DAI (Days After Inoculation)	45
13	Growth inhibition of <i>A. brassicicola</i> on PDA plates, here, Control and containing 0.2% of A) Fiesta, B) Blitox, C) Metaril, D) Endofil, E) Cabrio, F) Bounty, G) Awal, H) Companion, I) Eminent, J) Autostin, K) Rovral and L) Contaf	46

CHAPTER I

Introduction

Mustard (*Brassica juncea*) and rapeseed (*Brassica napus*) belong to the family Brassicaceae are currently ranked as the world's third important oil crop in terms of area and production. In Bangladesh, mustard-rapeseed is the most important oilseed crop after soybean with a total cultivated area of 0.325 million hectares and production was 0.359 million Mt & yield 1104.09 Kg ha⁻¹ in 2014-2015 (BBS, 2015) Mustard seeds are used for the extraction of oil, in the preparation of vegetables, curries and pickles as a condiment. Mustard-rapeseed can be grown in a tropical as well as in temperate zone. Due to rapid increase of area cultivated with mustard-rapeseed as well as lack of resistance in current mustard-rapeseed cultivars, infection by pathogens such as *Alternaria brassicicola* has become a threat to the production of this oil crop, causing a loss of 35 to 70 percent seed yield (Kolte, 1985, Singh and Singh, 2005).

A huge number of diseases may occur worldwide in mustard-rapeseed including Bangladesh. Black leaf spot of mustard-rapeseed is one of them. Black leaf spot of mustard-rapeseed caused by *A. brassicicola* results in 25-50% yield reductions (Rotem, 1994). The greatest yield loss of *Alternaria* black spot comes from pod shatter. This disease also reduces seed quality, seed weight, decreases protein of seed and the percent germination in harvested seed. In its early stages, it only affects the plants slightly by reducing photosynthesis, however as the plant matures it can cause damage to the seeds and more, reducing oil yield as well. This disease causes an average yield loss of 40-70% in India and 30-60% in Bangladesh (Meah *et al.*, 1988).

Due to the lack of resistance sources against *A. brassicae* and *A. brassicicola* in Brassicaceae family, *Alternaria* leaf spot is considered the most damaging and widespread fungal disease of *Brassica*. Since *Alternaria* leaf spot is increasingly

destructive in oil production, ways of controlling the disease need to be developed. Resistant varieties are required to stabilize seed production. It should be mentioned that it's very difficult, laborious, costly and time-consuming to develop a resistant variety against *Alternaria* leaf blight disease. In addition, various cultural and biological control methods are not effective in the field conditions due to various alternate hosts present in the growing season. In addition, the use of several fungicides increase the production cost of the farmers and creates environmental pollutions creating a health hazard. Thus it is mandatory to find out the effective fungicides and their appropriate doses to control *Alternaria* leaf spot of mustard-rapeseed.

However, chemical fungicide is the only viable way for the control of this disease in the field in Bangladesh. Till to date from the last couple of decades Rovral®, a fungicide belong to Iprodione chemical group was identified to effectively control this disease but which is expensive for the growers. To overcome this problem it is necessary to find out an alternative and effective fungicide with the appropriate dose. Next generation fungicides (especially newly arrived fungicides with the new combination) which are available in the market can be used for controlling this disease in Bangladesh. However, continuous and indiscriminate use of some fungicides often leads to development of fungicide resistance in pathogen (Gangawane, 1997) and also spraying of different fungicides are uneconomical and inconsistent (Jones, 2000) to manage the disease moreover field efficacy of some newly arrived fungicide i.e. next generation fungicides against this *Alternaria* blight of mustard-rapeseed disease in Bangladesh is inadequate.

The insight of the above backgrounds, the present investigation was undertaken with the following objectives:

- To compare the efficacy of twelve fungicides of different chemical groups against *Alternaria brassicicola* in *in vitro* condition.
- To determine the effective dosage of selective fungicides against *Alternaria brassicicola* in the field condition.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Alternaria leaf blight or black leaf spot caused by *Alternaria brassicicola* is one of the important diseases of brassica oilseeds and cruciferous vegetables. Till to date, the chemical approach is the most suitable way for the effective field control of this disease in Bangladesh. However, the following information was reviewed in favour of the present study, which was performed elsewhere in the world and Bangladesh relevant to the present study.

2.1. Literatures on *Alternaria* leaf blight disease of mustard-rapeseed

Kolte (2002) described *Alternaria* blight of rapeseed-mustard (*Brassica* spp.) caused by *Alternaria brassicae* (Berk.) Sacc., is one of the most important limiting factors, causing yield losses of up to 35–45% in mustard (*Brassica juncea*).

Verma and Saharan (1994) found that *Alternaria* spp. is reported to affect the host plant at all growth stages and infects all the aerial tissues and seeds. The pathogen causes the slow destruction of the host plant by reducing the photosynthetic potential. The symptoms first appear on the lower leaves as minute brown to black dots that rapidly multiply and enlarge to form prominent round spots with concentric rings of different shape, size and color. As the disease progresses, the complete leaf gets affected and ultimately defoliates. At the later stages of plant growth, the spots appear on the stem and siliquae generally in the form of black stripes which subsequently coalesce, turning the siliqua black. The decaying of the seeds can be seen just beneath the black spots of siliqua. Severe infection on the stem and pods leads to premature ripening, resulting in yield losses due to seed shedding.

Conn and Tewari (1990) observed that among the different diseases caused by the genus *Alternaria*, blight disease is one of the most dominant ones that causes average yield loss in the range of 32-57% in different host crops.

Conn et al. (1990) mentioned that *Alternaria brassicae* infect the plant at all growth stages. This fungus infects all parts of the plant as leaves, pods, branches, pods and stem but the special target point of the fungus are leaves and pods. Often lesions are produced on green leaves and during severe attack in pods, seeds become shrivel and early ripening or shattering.

Valkonen & Koponen (1990) described symptoms of *Alternaria* leaf blight disease of mustard include the presence of irregular, often circular brown to dark brown colour leaf spots having concentric lines within the spots. Disease symptoms first appear on older leaves as small necrotic spots that may be surrounded by a yellow halo. Often the circular spots coalesce to form large patches resulting in the leaf blight. In quite a few cases dark colored small spots are also formed on pods and tender twigs.

Humpherson-Jones et al. (1989) said that infected crops left on the ground after harvest also serve as a source of infection for *A. brassicae* and *A. brassicicola*. In one study, infected leaves of oilseed rape and cabbage placed outdoors on soil, produced viable spores for as long as leaf tissues remained intact. For oilseed rape this was up to 8 weeks and for cabbage up to 12 weeks.

Sinha and Prasad (1989) reported that *Alternaria* blight caused by *Alternaria brassicae* and/or *A. brassicicola* is one of the limiting factors in cauliflower curd quality and seed production as it reduces the number of grains/siliqua and impairs the quality in respect to seed vitality.

Kadian and Saharan (1983) mentioned that the initial infection on the lower leaves starts as minute brown to blackish lesions, which multiply rapidly and later spread

to the upper leaves, stem and siliqua. On the leaves formation of concentric rings in the lesions and a zone of yellow halo around the lesions is very prominent.

Maude (1980) found that *A. brassicae* either alone or in combination with *A. brassicicola* and other secondary invaders attack and blacken the fruit-bearing branches, pods and seeds in cauliflower resulting in considerable losses. In addition, the harvested seed samples were light in weight and had low viability.

Chupp & Sherf (1960) reported that infected seeds, with spores on the seed coat or mycelium under the seed coat, are likely the main source of transport for *Alternaria* pathogens. Spores are disseminated by wind, water, tools and animals. The fungus can survive in susceptible weeds or perennial crops.

2.2. Literatures on *Alternaria brassicicola* and *A. brassicae* pathogens

Singh et al. (2015) observed that during the growing season, spores are spread by wind, water, and field equipment. Infection requires leaf wetness, which allows spores to enter through pores in the leaves. Lesions appear 3-5 days later and soon become a source for new inoculums.

Aneja and Agnihotri (2013) said that *A. brassicae* and *A. brassicicola*, the causal agents of the disease *Alternaria* blight, are cosmopolitan in occurrence. Both the species are known to damage the vegetable crucifers, *A. brassicae* being most ravaging on oil yielding brassicas. The pathogen is characterized as pseudo-fungi, with the absence of an identifiable sexual stage. The key taxonomic features of the pathogen are the production of large, obclavate, olive-grey to dark-coloured conidia, having longitudinal as well as transverse septae.

Nowicki et al. (2012) described that *Alternaria* black spot of cruciferous vegetables, incited by different species of *Alternaria*, remains an increasing threat to *Brassicaceae*

crops throughout the world, including Poland. *Brassica* plants are attacked by conidia of *A. brassicae* (Berk.) Sacc., *A. brassicicola* (Schw.) Wiltsh., *A. raphani* Groves & Skolko, and *A. alternata* (Fr.) Kreissler. The pathogens have a wide spectrum of hosts, such as head cabbage, Chinese cabbage, cauliflower, broccoli, and other crucifers including cultivated and wild grown plants. *Alternaria* pathogens usually cause damping-off of seedlings, spotting of leaves of cabbages, blackleg of heads of cabbages, and spotting of cauliflower curds and broccoli florets. In oilseed rape, *A. brassicae* is the dominant invasive species, while in the cruciferous vegetables, both species, *A. brassicae*, and *A. brassicicola* are encountered. Infected seeds with spores on the seed coat or mycelium under the seed coat are the main means of distribution for these pathogens. The fungus can overwinter on susceptible weeds or crop debris and on seed plants.

Sangeetha and Siddaramaiah (2007) said that the maximum temperature of 26-29°C and a minimum temperature of 14 -15 °C and average relative humidity more than 65 % were found most favourable for the development of white rust downy mildew and *Alternaria* blight in Indian mustard.

Doullah et al. (2006) suggested that 5×10^4 *A. brassicicola* conidia ml⁻¹ is the optimal inoculum concentration at which various levels of resistance in *B. rapa* genotypes can be effectively distinguished. The severity of the dark leaf spot increased with increasing incubation temperature and symptom severity between 25°C and 30°C did not differ significantly in both the resistant and susceptible cultivars.

Kumar (2006) reported that the temperature ranged from 21 - 23°C and 23 - 27°C favoured for the mycelial growth of *A. brassicae* and *A. brassicicola* respective in *in vitro*. Lower temperature (23 °C) was found optimum for growth of *A. brassicae* as compared to 25°C for *A. brassicicola*. Maximum sporulation was supported by 23 - 25°C temperature for *A. brassicae*, whereas 23 - 27°C temperature supported maximum sporulation for *A. brassicicola*.

Bart (2003) described that *Alternaria* species are mainly saprophytic fungi. Some species of *Alternaria* genus have acquired pathogenic capacities collectively causing disease over a broad range of host. The systematic classification of *Alternaria* spp. is as known Kingdom- fungi, Subkingdom- Eumycota, Phylum - Fungi imperfecti, class- Hymenomycetes, order - Moniliales, family - Dematiaceae and genus - *Alternaria*. *A. raphani* is very similar to *A. brassicae*, from which it differs in the formation of chlamydospore and in a shorter beak of conidium. *A. brassicae* appears to be most prevalent. Conidia of *A. brassicae* measure 75 to 350 picometre (pm) long and usually 20 to 30 pm thick in the broadest part.

Pandey (2002) found that the *Alternaria* pathogen grows on a temperature range of 5°C to 45°C. The optimum temperature for growth and sporulation was followed by 30°C. The pathogen was able to tolerate a wide pH range (3.5 to 9.0) but followed by 6.0 as most suitable for growth and sporulation.

Ahamad & Narain (2000) reported that the disease appeared in the first fortnight of July and maximum disease intensity was noticed when the temperature ranged in between 25 to 28°C and average relative humidity was more than 80%. Rainfall was held greatly responsible for the severity of infection and disease development.

Rotem (1994) described that the *Alternaria* is a cosmopolitan genus found worldwide in association with a wide variety of substrates. Many species are saprophytes commonly found in soil, decaying plant tissues, wood, wood pulp, compost and unusual substrates such as sewage or jet fuel.

Evans (1992) observed that increasing in leaf wetness duration, disease severity increases at all temperatures. The maximum observed mean disease severity occurred after 24 hrs duration of wetness at 18°C.

Paul (1992) reported that different species of *Alternaria* on *Brassica* spp. vary in host specificity. *Alternaria brassicae* also depending on host susceptibility and environmental factors.

Duhan and Suhag (1990) studied the effect of inoculum density of pathogen *A. brassicae*, agronomic practice and meteorological factors on *Alternaria* blight of cauliflower under glasshouse and field conditions. The disease severity increased with close spacing, high relative humidity, intermittent drizzling and moderate temperature at pod setting.

2.3 Effect of chemical fungicides in controlling *Alternaria* and *Alternaria* pathogens

Kumar et al. (2017) found that in *in vitro* evaluation of the botanicals drake (*Melia azedarach*) had the highest efficacy of 63.52 percent inhibition of the average mycelial growth of the *Alternaria solani*. However the least effective botanical was *Urtica dioica* with 36.30 per cent of mycelial inhibition. Among the fungicides, most effective was Score which inhibited the mycelial growth up to 78.61 percent followed by 76.67 per cent of carbendazim. Minimum inhibition of the mycelial growth was recorded in kavach (50.74%). Under *in vivo* (pots) evaluation, the highest efficacy of Score was recorded when sprayed at 0.05 percent concentration with disease severity of 16.33 percent and disease control of 74.89 per cent followed by carbendazim fungicide (18.00%, 72.30%) when compared with control while the least efficacy was observed with the fungicides kavach (33.67%, 48.22%) and insignia (26.00%, 60.00%).

Ahmad & Ashraf (2016) reported that six plant extracts, six biological agents and six fungicides were evaluated both *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiment for their effectiveness to manage *Alternaria* leaf spot of *Brassica campestris*. In the field, Wisdom (50% WP) and Proctor fungicides were used @ 0.2%. Out of all fungicides, the maximum growth inhibition (in laboratory 98.79%, in field 56.08% and in greenhouse 63%) was found by Wisdom (50% WP) and followed by Proctor (60% WP) (in laboratory 100%, in field 51.76% and in greenhouse 55.16%). It was worth noting that the fungicides, Wisdom (50% WP) and Proctor (60% WP) had highest net value as compared to other treatments but the biological agents also showed off their importance.

Mahapatra & Das (2016) used three fungicides (iprodione, propiconazole, mancozeb) in a field trial with four different doses (0.15, 0.20, 0.25, 0.30% a.i.) for the control of *Alternaria* blight of mustard during the year 2008-09 to 2009-10 in Nadia, Mohanpur, West Bengal, India. All the three fungicides reduced the *Alternaria* blight disease severity in comparison to untreated control irrespective of their doses. The results showed that three sprayings at 15 days interval from 40 days after sowing showed minimum percent of leaf infection (13.0%), AUDPC (9.9), percent of siliqua infection (9.9%), number of spots per siliqua (5.3) and increase in the number of siliqua per plant (106.0) and seed yield (kg/ha) in iprodione sprayed plots @ 0.25% (1682.6 kg/ha) similar as @ 0.3% a.i. of the same chemicals (1671.8 kg/ha) and followed by propiconazole @ 0.30% (1539.3 kg/ha) with maximum cost-benefit ratio (1:5.5, 1:4.5 and 1:3.5, respectively).

Sadana et al. (2015) investigated the efficacy of seven fungicides (mancozeb, captan, thiram, copper sulphate, carbendazim, zineb and copper oxychloride) and they found that all the fungicides reduced the disease severity as compared to the untreated check. The highest reduction in the disease was achieved by applying mancozeb (1500 ppm) that caused 86.4 percent inhibition of mycelial growth in A1 strain of *Alternaria solani* in *in vitro* condition.

Gondal et al. (2012) stated that different doses of mancozeb (4 g/L, 8 g/L, 12 g/L and 16 g/L of water) were applied after 7 days intervals for control of *Alternaria* blight of tomato. The highest reduction in the disease was achieved by applying mancozeb 12 g/L of water at an interval of 7, 14, 21 and 28 days. They also described that weekly sprays of mancozeb at 12 g/L of water were cost-effective and eco-friendly for the management of *Alternaria* blight of tomato.

Nowicki et al. (2012) stated that methods for *Alternaria* black spot disease prevention and control are based on combining agricultural management practices with chemical control. Using disease-free seeds or seeds treated with fungicides can greatly reduce disease incidence. After the appearance of the first symptoms of the disease, stringent fungicide spray program is an effective way to reduce losses.

Verma (2010) reported that three sprayings of Dithane M-45 (0.25%), Kavach (0.1%) or Foltol (0.25%) at 10 days interval significantly reduced the radial growth of the fungus in *in vitro* experiment. However, hexaconazole was very effective as it caused 100% growth inhibition.

Sultana et al. (2009) conducted a field experiment to identify the appropriate time of single application of Rovral® in controlling *Alternaria* blight disease of mustard. Results revealed that single spray of Rovral® @ 2 g per liter of water at 30, 40, 50 and 60 days after sowing (DAS) controlled the disease severity of leaf blight compared to 70 DAS and control. These results indicate that disease severity, seed yield and yield contributing characters were significantly influenced by variety and single time of spray. Three time application of Rovral® produced the lowest disease severity and produced highest seed yield. The highest seed yield (1747.33 kg ha⁻¹), lowest disease severity (1.7) and PDI (8.89) were recorded from the treatment combination (BARI Sarisa-9 with 3 sprays). The second highest seed yield (1588.10 kg ha⁻¹) and lowest severity (2.0) were obtained from treatment combination (BARI Sarisa-9) with single spraying Rovral® at 50 DAS.

Singh (2008) found three sprays of 0.25% Ridomil MZ (i.e. @ 2kg/ha) at 10 days intervals were most effective in controlling early blight of potato caused by *A. solani* followed by Melody Duo 66.75 WP (@ 2.5kg/ha and 2 kg/ha) and Antracol 70 WP.

Khan et al. (2007) evaluated the efficacy of three systemic fungicides: Topsin-M (Thiophanate methyl, 70%WP), Ridomil MZ (Mancozeb, 64% +Metalaxyl, 8%WP), and Bavistin (Carbendazim, 50%WP) alone and in combination with four non-systemic fungicides such as Captaf (Captan, 50%WP), Indofil M-45 (Mancozeb, 75%WP), Indofil Z-78 (Zineb, 75%WP), and Thiram (Thiram, 75%WP) both *in vitro* and *in vivo* for their effectiveness to manage Alternaria blight of rapeseed-mustard caused by *Alternaria brassicae*. A pure culture of the pathogenic fungus was applied in the field @ 2g colonized sorghum seeds kg⁻¹ soil. All the fungicides were evaluated for their efficacy at various concentrations, 50, 100, 150, 200 and 500 ppm, and were sprayed in the field @ 0.2%. All fungicides significantly reduced the disease but Ridomil MZ was most effective. Topsin-M at a concentration of 500 ppm was the most effective in reducing the radial growth of the pathogenic fungi (74.2%). Ridomil MZ reduced disease severity by 32% and was followed in effectiveness by the combination Bavistin+Captaf (26.5%). Maximum yield was obtained in plots sprayed with Bavistin+Captaf (1198 kg/ha) followed by Bavistin+Indofil Z-78 (1172 kg/ha). It was worth nothing that the highest net profit, as well as the highest cost-benefit ratio, was obtained with Bavistin+Indofil Z-78 (1:3.2), followed by Bavistin+Captaf (1:1.3).

Abdel (2007) mentioned that the potassium and sodium bicarbonate and Nerol (a commercial product of the citrus essential oil fractions) had great inhibitory effect against *A. solani* causing early blight of potato. Complete inhibition of fungus was obtained with potassium or sodium bicarbonate at 2% and Nerol at 0.5%.

Singh and Singh (2006) tested the efficacy of seven fungicides *viz.*, Chlorothalonil, Copper oxychloride, Azoxystrobin, Propineb, Copper hydroxide, Mancozeb at different concentration i.e, 2500, 2000, 1000, 500 and 250 ppm and Hexaconazole

against *A. alternata* at 1000, 500, 200, 100 and 50 ppm causing blight of tomato. Their observations revealed that the radial growth of the fungus significantly reduced by the use of all the fungicides whereas hexaconazole was very effective as it caused 100% growth inhibition.

Prasad and Naik (2003) found iprodione, mancozeb and copper oxychloride as most effective and thus inhibited more than 75.00 percent of mycelial growth at 0.25 percent concentration followed by thiophanate methyl at 0.1 percent, whereas carbendazim and benomyl were not effective against *A. solani*.

Prasad and Naik (2003) reported that Mancozeb followed by Thiram, Bavistin and Iprodione also proved effective as seed dresser for *Alternaria solani*. Among non-systemic fungicides Iprodione and Mancozeb and among systemic fungicides thiophanate methyl was found to be effective under *in vitro* conditions.

Patil (2003) evaluated the efficacy of fungicides namely carbendazim (0.5%), and mancozeb (0.25%), botanicals i.e. neem seed and leaf extract each at 5% concentration and tobacco decoction (@.2%) against the early blight of tomato. The lowest percentage of disease incidence was observed in carbendazim (13.93%), and mancozeb (15.46%) treatments.

Singh & Rai (2003) found that Indofil Z-78, Vitavax, Indofil M-45 and Kavach most effective in reducing the mycelial growth of *A. alternata* infecting brinjal in *in vitro* followed by Thiram, Bavistin and Benlate.

Sidlauskiene et al. (2003) stated that Amistar was very effective in controlling leaf spot of *Alternaria* in tomato, cucumber and cabbage as it reduces the disease incidence by 88-93%.

Tofoli (2003) observed that the highest level of early blight control, quality, and increase on fruit yield of potato with pyraclostrobin+metiram, fenamidone+

chlorothalonil, femoxadone + cymoxanil + mancozeb, kresoxim + methyl, Azoxystrobin, difenoconazole, tebuconazole, pyrimethanil, cyprodinil, femoxadone + mancozeb followed by prochloraz, fluazinam, procymidone, and iprodione, while mancozeb and chlorothalonil resulted in the lowest level of control.

Tomescu (2002) reported that spraying of different combinations of the fungicides such as 0.2% Dithane M-45, 0.15% Funguran OH (50% CuOH), 0.25% Curzatemanox (5% cymoxanil + 18% mancozeb + 50% oxychloride), 0.2% Dithane M-45 + 0.1% Bavistin, 0.15% Funguran OH + 0.2% Dithane + 0.1% Bavistin + Ridomil plus Gold (2.5% metalaxyl + 40% copper oxychloride) at every ten days interval with weed control, and removal of infected tomato fruits resulted disease control up to 81.0%.

Katiyar et al. (2001) observed that the best control of *Alternaria* leaf spot disease of bottle gourd was obtained by spraying recommended dose i.e. 0.2% Indofil M-45 followed by Copper oxychloride, Chlorothalonil, Indofil Z-78, Ridomil, Cuman L, Jkstein and Topsin-M.

Ansari et al. (1990) evaluated eighteen fungicides as to their control of *A. brassicae* in artificial cultures, infected seeds, and as a foliar spray on infected plants of *B. campestris* var. *yellow sarson* (a highly susceptible rape cultivar). Throughout the study Dithane M-45 (Mancozeb) and Dithane Z-78 (Zineb) consistently provided the best control data. Seven fungicides completely inhibited the growth of the pathogen in *in vitro* culture: Benlate a@ 0.1%, Dithane M-45, Dithane Z-78, Ziram, Difolatan-80 and Thiram @ 0.2% and Blitox-50 @ 0.3 %. As a seed dressing, Benlate @ 0.1% provided the best control with a mean loss of 4.5 pre-emergence seedlings and 6.5 post-emergence seedlings per pot (25 seeds planted in each pot, 8 pots). Dithane M-45 and Dithane Z-78, both applied @ 0.2% had a mean pre-emergence seedling loss of 10.5 and 11.25, respectively and post-emergence seedling loss of 11.5 and 13.75, respectively. As a foliar spray, Dithane M-45 (@ 0.2%) provided significantly better control over other fungicides, including Benlate. Dithane M-45

gave better results than Dithane Z-78 (@ 0.2%), although the difference was not significant. Plants treated with these two fungicides also provided the highest seed yields.

Nisar (1990) evaluated eighteen fungicides for their effects on the growth of *Alternaria brassicae* ascertaining their fungicidal fungistatic natures in an artificial medium. Eighteen fungicides were first evaluated for their effects on the growth of *Alternaria brassicae* and for ascertaining their fungicidal and fungistatic natures in artificial cultures. The chemicals emerging fungicidal in action were later evaluated for their efficacy as a seed treatment and foliar application in the management of damping-off of seedlings and blight of rapeseed separately. Of 18 fungicides tested, six fungicides, viz., Dithane M-45, Dithane Z-78, Ziram, Difolatan-80, Blitox-50 and Benlate completely inhibited the growth of the pathogen and were fungicidal in action. Thiram and Brestan-60, which also caused total growth inhibition Benlate (0.1) followed by Dithane M-45 was best seed-dressing fungicide for controlling damping-off of seedlings. Dithane M-45 (0.2~) followed by Dithane Z-78 as the foliar spray was most effective for controlling the blight and increasing the yield in field trials.

CHAPTER III

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present research work was conducted to evaluate the efficacy of some new and mixed fungicides and their effective doses on controlling *Alternaria* leaf blight or black leaf spot disease incited by *Alternaria brassicicola* under laboratory and field conditions.

3.1. Laboratory experiment

3.1.1. Experimental Site

The laboratory experiment was conducted in the Plant-Microbe Interaction Laboratory, Department of Plant Pathology, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh.

3.1.2. Experimental period

This *in vitro* research work was performed during the period from September 2016 - June 2017.

3.1.3. Experimental design

The lab experiment was done following Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replications for each of the treatments.

3.1.4. Collection, Isolation and identification of *Alternaria brassicicola* isolate

Isolate of *Alternaria brassicicola* obtained from infected mustard seeds which were collected from farmers. Standard blotter method (ISTA, 1996) was used for the isolation of this *Alternaria* pathogen. In this blotter method, 25 (1+8+16) mustard seeds were placed on blotter paper (moistened with water drop) in plastic petridishes. Then the petridishes were incubated at the incubation room at 20-25°C

and after 10 days pathogenic structures (mycelia) on seeds were observed under a stereo binocular microscope. Then the infested seeds were maintained on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium for 10 days in the incubation room to grow and ensure the concern pathogen by preparing a slide and compared the morphological characters.

A standard amount of fungal material was transferred to the centre of a fresh PDA plate using a sterilized block cutter. The plates were sealed with parafilm and all isolates then grown under optimum incubated conditions for 10 days. Sequential culturing from fungal stock was done for 5-7 times to get a pure culture (1st stock used as mother stock for 2nd, 2nd for 3rd and so on), that was used for inoculation.

Inoculation was done from stock culture under the laminar airflow cabinet to avoid contamination and get a pure culture. The incubation temperature during this period was 24°C with alternate 12/12 h UV light and darkness. The materials used for pure culture were sterilized properly.

3.1.5. Fungicides and their specification

In this study different fungicides from different chemical groups (**Table 1**) with five different concentrations of each were used in the *in vitro* inhibition test.

Table 1. List of Fungicides along with their active ingredients used in this study

Fungicide Name (Trade name of chemical)	Active ingredient	Company name	Concentration (%)
Autostin 50WP	Carbendazim 50%	Auto Crop Care Ltd.	(0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2)
Indofil M45	Mancozeb 80%		(0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2)
Companion	Mancozeb 63% +		(0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2)

	Carbendazim 12%		
Awual 72WP	Zineb 68%+ Hexaconazol 14%		(0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2)
Blitox 50WP	Copper oxychloride (50%)		(0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2)
Rovral 50WP	Iprodione 50%		(0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2)
Fiesta Z-78	Zinc-Ethylene-bis- di-thio- Carbamate		(0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2)
Metaril 72 WP	Mancozeb 64%+Metalaxyl 8%		(0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2)
Contaf 5EC	Hexaconazol 50%		(0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2)
Eminent Pro	Tetraconazol 12.5%+ Carbendazim 15%	Shetu Pesticides Limited	(0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2)
Cabrio Top	Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram (55%)	BASF Bangladesh Limited	(0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2)
Baounty	Glyphosate (glycine)	Shetu Pesticides Limited	(0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2)

3.1.6. Preparation of Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium

PDA medium is the most commonly used medium and is useful for the group of many fungi.

Composition:

Potato (peeled and sliced): 200g

Dextrose: 20g

Agar: 15g

Water: 1000ml

For this preparation, 200g of clean peeled potato slices were boiled in 500 ml of water. Water was separated from boiled potato slices through a cotton cloth. Then 20g Dextrose and 15g Agar were added to the boiled water and made the final volume 1000 ml of PDA medium. The pH of the medium was adjusted to 5.6. The medium was dispensed to the flask, plunged and autoclaved for 15 minutes at 15 lb atmospheric pressure. Then the PDA medium was poured into petridishes for the preparation of PDA plate for subsequent study.

3.1.7. Preparation of PDA containing fungicides

To prepare the 0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2% solution of twelve different fungicides with PDA medium, 0.125, 0.25, 0.5, 1 and 2 g of each of them were taken in 1 liter autoclaved PDA medium and stirred properly with the help of magnetic stirrer. Then the PDA media containing different fungicides with different concentration were poured into petridishes for the preparation of the PDA plate of the subsequent study. By this way, PDA plates supplemented with fungicides were prepared.

3.1.8. Inoculation of PDA plate with *A. brassicicola*

PDA plates supplemented with different fungicides with different concentrations were inoculated with a pure culture of *A. brassicicola*. In brief, mycelial blocks were cut out of 10 days old fungal colony near the margin with a sterilized cork borer of 5 mm diameter. These blocks were placed at the center of the petri plates with of a sterilized inoculating needle. For each of the treatments, three replications were maintained. All these were done under an aseptic condition under a laminar airflow cabinet which was sterilized previously by spraying 70% Ethanol.

After 10 days, the mycelial growth of *A. brassicicola* was recorded by measuring the average of two diameters at right angles to one another. The same procedures were repeated three times and mean of mycelial growth was calculated.

Then the efficacy of the fungicides was calculated as percent growth inhibition using the following formula reported by Satish et al. (2007); Dubey et al. (2009).

$$\text{Growth inhibition (\%)} = \frac{(C - T)}{C} \times 100$$

Where,

C = Mean mycelial growth (radial) of pathogen in control plate

T = Mean mycelial growth (radial) of pathogen in treatment

3.1.9. Collection of data

Data on different parameters viz. radial mycelia growth and percent growth inhibition were recorded.

3.1.10. Data analysis

The data on different parameters were statistically analyzed by using analysis of variance (ANOVA) technique to find out the level of significance (Gomez and Gomez, 1984). The effect of the treatments was compared by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT). The collected data were analyzed using a statistical computer package SAS (University Edition version 3.71 basic edition) statistical package.

3.2. Field experiment

3.2.1. Experimental site

The experiment was conducted in the field laboratory of Agronomy field laboratory, Department of Agronomy, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh.

3.2.2. Experimental period

The experiment was performed during the period from late October 2017 to January 2018.

3.2.3. Crop and Variety

BARI Sarisha 14, one of the high yielding variety of mustard in Bangladesh was used for the field experiment. This variety is also susceptible to *Alternaria* blight disease.

3.2.4. Preparation of experimental plot

The soil of the field was medium high land with well-drained clay loam textured soil having a pH value of 6.9 belongs to Old Brahmaputra Floodplain (AEZ-9). In total, 60 plots were prepared for 3 treatments including control (where 27 for one spray and another 27 for double spray and rest 6 plots for control) and each of the treatment maintained with 3 replications. Each chemical treatment used in this experiment had four different concentrations. The plot size was 1m².

3.2.5. Sowing of seed

Seeds in each plot were sown on 15 November 2017. Thinning was done at 30 days after sowing (DAS) to maintain the optimum plant population.

3.2.6. Fertilizer application

The following fertilizers were applied in each plot as per the recommended dose of the Fertilizer Recommendation Guide (BARC, 2012).

Urea, Triple superphosphate, Muriate of potash and Borax were applied at the time of final land preparation at sowing date except for urea. The one-third of the Urea

and the total amount of TSP, MOP, Gypsum and Boric acid were applied in the soil during field preparation. Rest of the urea was applied in two equal splits at 30 and 45 days after sowing (DAS).

Fertilizer	Dose (Kg/h)	Dose(g/plot)
Urea	190	19
Triple Super Phosphate(TSP)	140	14
Muriate of Potash(MOP)	100	10
Gypsum	120	12
Borax	10	0.1

3.2.7. Intercultural operation

Weeding was done in all the plots as per requirement. Irrigation was applied from time to time when required.

Weeding

Observation the field after weeding

Data collection

Figure 1: Different Field Activities (Weeding, Observation, Data Collections) are done by Researcher

3.2.8. Treatments

Based on *in vitro* result two best-performed fungicides with four different concentrations were used to know their effect on the disease incidence and severity of Alternaria blight of mustard and different yield contributing parameters of mustard. The following nine treatments including control were used in this field experiment.

Treatments	Fungicides	Concentration
T0	Control	-
T1	Rovral	0.0125%
T2	Rovral	0.025%
T3	Rovral	0.05%
T4	Rovral	0.1%
T5	Contaf	0.0125%
T6	Contaf	0.025%
T7	Contaf	0.05%
T8	Contaf	0.1%

3.2.9. Preparation of spray fungicide solution

To prepare 0.0125%, 0.025%, 0.05% and 0.1% solution of Rovral, 0.125, 0.25, 0.5 and 1g fungicides were taken respectively in four different 1000 ml volumetric flasks and then 1000 ml of distilled water was added in each of the flasks up to the mark of the flask. After that, the content within the flask was stirred properly with the

help of a magnetic stirrer. By this way, 0.0125%, 0.025%, 0.05% and 0.1% solutions of Rovral were prepared.

On the other hand, to prepare 0.0125%, 0.025%, 0.05% and 0.1% solution of Contaf, 125, 250, 500 and 1000 µl fungicides were taken respectively in four different 1000 ml volumetric flasks and then required amount of distilled water was added in each of the flasks up to the mark of the flask. After that the content within the flask was stirred properly and these way four different Contaf solutions were prepared.

3.2.10. Application of fungicide solution

Fungicide solutions were sprayed onto the plant surface as per treatments in two instalments. In this experiment, 60 plots were prepared and among these plots, 27 plots were sprayed once at 40 DAS and 27 plots were sprayed twice at 40 and 50 DAS with different fungicide solutions. Rest of the six plots i.e. three control plots were maintained for each of the time points.

3.2.11. Assessment of disease incidence and severity

In each of the plot 10 plants were considered randomly to find out the disease incidence by using the following formula-

$$\text{Disease incidence (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of infected plants}}{\text{Total no. of plants}} \times 100$$

Disease severity of naturally infected BARI Sharisha-14 plants in 60 plots was assessed by a disease severity scale (Table 2) according to King (1994). In this experiment 10 plants were considered randomly for each of the plots for the assessment of disease severity. The disease severity was measured at 40 and 50 DAS i.e. five (5) days after spray application.

Table 2: Disease severity scale (King, 1994)

Disease severity index	Symptoms produced on leaves
1	No spots and no chlorosis on the leaf
2	A few pinpoint spots but no chlorosis
3	Some spots but no large lesions and no chlorosis
4	Some spots with a few lesions surrounded by light chlorosis
5-9	Increasing number and size of lesions and chlorosis on the leaf
10	Lesions with chlorosis on more than 90% of the leaf

Figure 2: Scale for assessing disease severity for Alternaria leaf blight of mustard (King, 1994)

3.2.12. Harvesting of crop

The crop was harvested on 21 January 2018, plot-wise when 90% of siliqua was matured. The harvested plants were tied into bundles and carried to the threshing floor. The plants were sun-dried by spreading the bundles on the threshing floor. The seeds were separated from the stover by beating the bundles with bamboo sticks.

3.2.13. Data collection for the yield contributing parameters

Ten plants plot⁻¹ were selected randomly for data collection. The sample plants were uprooted separately prior to harvest and dried properly in the sun. The seed yield was recorded after cleaning and drying under the sun.

Data on the following parameters were collected during the maturity stage of the plant.

- 1. Plant height:** The height of the plants was measured from the ground level to the tip of the topmost pods.
- 2. Pods plant⁻¹:** Number of pods for each plant was counted.
- 3. Pod length:** Length of each pod was measured from the average often.
- 4. Seeds pod⁻¹:** Seeds were collected by splitting five pods from each plant out of ten plants and then counted the seed.
- 5. Weight of 1000-seeds:** Thousand seeds of each plot were counted and weighed with a fine electric balance.
- 6. Seed yield:** By threshing the plants of each plot, the seed weight was taken and converted the yield into kg ha⁻¹.

3.2.14. Data analysis

The experiment was conducted in RCBD with three replications. The data on different parameters were statistically analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) technique to find out the level of significance (Gomez and Gomez, 1984). The treatment means were compared by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at 5% level of significance. The collected data were analyzed using SAS (University Edition version 3.71 basic edition) statistical package.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS

4.1. Laboratory Experiment

4.1.1. Isolation and identification of *Alternaria brassicicola*

The fungus grew up out of seeds in moist blotter in 3-4 days of incubation. Deep brown to dark ashy structures appeared on seeds. Each seed with such structure was observed under a stereo-binocular microscope. Primarily confirmed, the bushes were of *Alternaria* (Figure 3).

On transfer to PDA plates, colonies with dark color top and back appeared. Slides prepared out of such a colony when observed under a microscope confirmed the fungus as *A. brassicicola* (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Pure culture of *Alternaria brassicicola* (A) and different Structures of *Alternaria brassicicola* (B).

4.1.2 Effect of different fungicides at 0.0125% concentration on radial mycelial growth of *Alternaria brassicicola* over control at 10 Days after Inoculation

Effect of different fungicides at 0.0125% concentration on the radial mycelia growth of *A. brassicicola* were observed significant in this study. The result revealed that

there was no radial mycelia growth (cm) occurred in plates containing Rovral 50WP (Iprodion 50%), Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazole 50%) and Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%) significantly lower mycelial growth was observed in Eminent Pro (Tetraconazol 12.5%+ Carbendazim 15%), Companion (Mancozeb 63%+Carbendazim 12%) and while the maximum radial mycelial growth was recorded in control plates and plates containing by Fiesta (Zinc ethylene-bis-dithio Carbamate), Blitox 50WP (Copper oxychloride 50%) followed by Endofil M45 (Mancozeb 80%) (Figure 4). However, the medium radial mycelial growth was recorded in PDA plate containing Metaril 72WP (Mancozeb 64%+Metalaxyl 8%), Cabrio Top (Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram (55%)), Bounty (Glyphosate (glycine)) after 10 DAI (Table 3 and Figure 4).

Table 3: Mycelial growth of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.0125% of different fungicide(s) separately over control

Name of the fungicides	Mycelial Growth (cm) at 10 DAI*
T1= Control	9.00 a
T2= Fiesta	8.07 b
T3= Blitox	7.70 c
T4= Endofil	6.33 d
T5= Metaril	5.23 e
T6= Cabrio	5.07 e
T7= Bounty	5.00 e
T8= Awal	4.60 f
T9= Companion	4.58 f
T10= Eminent	2.15 g
T11= Atostin 50	0.00 h
T12= Rovral	0.00 h
T13= Contaf	0.00 h
LSD(0.05)*	0.3466

*LSD (0.05): Least Significant Difference. In a column, means followed by the same letter(s) are statistically similar at 5% level by DMRT

Figure 4: Status of radial mycelial growth of *Alternaria brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.0125% of different fungicide(s) separately compared to control at 10 DAI (Days After Inoculation)

4.1.3 Effect of different fungicides at 0.0125% on percent growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* at 10 DAI

Effect of twelve selected fungicides at 0.0125% concentration on the percent growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* was also observed in this study. The result showed that there was no growth inhibition occurred on the control plate. The minimum percent growth inhibition (10.37%) was recorded in plates containing Fiesta (Zinc ethylene-bis-dithio Carbamate) compared to control while the maximum inhibitions were recorded in the plates containing Rovral 50WP (Iprodion 50%), Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazole 50%), Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%), followed by Eminent Pro (Tetraconazol 12.5%+ Carbendazim 15%), with values 100%, 100%, 100% and 76.11% respectively. The moderate inhibition was recorded in PDA plate containing Metaril 72WP (Mancozeb 64%+Metalaxyl 8%), Cabrio Top (Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram (55%)), Bounty (Glyphosate (glycine)) with values

of 43.15%, 43.67% and 44.44% respectively (**Table 4, Figure 5**) after 10 days of inoculation.

Table 4: Percent mycelial growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.0125% of different fungicide(s) separately over control.

Name of the fungicides	% mycelial growth inhibition at 10 DAI
T1= Control	-
T2= Fiesta	10.37
T3= Blitox	14.25
T4= Endofil	30.37
T5= Metaril	43.14
T6= Cabrio	43.66
T7= <u>Bounty</u>	44.44
T8= Awal	48.88
T9= Companion	49.07
T10= Eminent	76.11
T11= Atostin 50	100.00
T12= Rovral	100.00
T13= Contaf	100.00

Figure 5: Growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates, here, Control and containing 0.0125% of A) Fiesta , B) Blitox, C) Endofil, D)Metaril, E) Cabrio, F) Bounty, G) Awal, H) Companion, I) Eminent, J) Autostin, K) Rovral and L) Contaf.

4.1.4 Effect of different fungicides at 0.025% concentration on radial mycelial growth of *Alternaria brassicicola* over control at 10 Days after Inoculation

Effect of different fungicides at 0.025% concentration on the radial mycelia growth of *A. brassicicola* were observed significant. No radial mycelial growth (cm) was recorded in plates containing Rovral 50WP (Iprodion 50%), Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazole 50%), Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%) followed by Eminent Pro (Tetraconazol 12.5%+ Carbendazim 15%) whereas the maximum radial mycelial growth was recorded in control plates and plates containing by Fiesta (Zinc ethylene-bis-dithio Carbamate) followed by Blitox 50WP (Copper oxychloride 50%), Indofil M45 (Mancozeb 80%), Metaril 72WP (Mancozeb 64%+Metalaxyl 8%) (Figure.6). However, the medium radial mycelial growth was recorded in PDA plate containing fungicides Cabrio Top (Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram (55%)), Bounty (Glyphosate (glycine)) (Table 5 and Figure 6).

Table 5: Mycelial growth of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.025% of different fungicide(s) separately over control.

Name	Mycelial Growth (cm) at 10 DAI*
T1= Control	9.00 a
T2= Fiesta	8.07 b
T3= Blitox	6.77 c
T4= Endofil	6.63 c
T5= Metaril	6.07 d
T6= Cabrio	5.15 e
T7= Bounty	5.00 e
T8= Awal	4.90 e
T9= Companion	4.15 f
T10= Eminent	2.62 g
T11= Atostin 50	0.00 h
T12= Rovral	0.00 h
T13= Contaf	0.00 h
LSD(0.05)*	0.2902

*LSD (0.05): Least Significant Difference. In a column, means followed by a same letter(s) are statistically similar at 5% level by DMRT

Figure 6: Status of radial mycelial growth of *Alternaria brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.025% of different fungicide(s) separately over control at 10 DAI (Days After Inoculation)

4.1.5 Effect of different fungicides at 0.025% on percent growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* at 10 DAI

Effect of twelve selected fungicides at 0.025% concentration on the per cent growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* was observed in this study. The result showed that there was no growth inhibition occurred on the control plate. The minimum percent growth inhibition (10.37%) was recorded in plates containing Fiesta (Zinc ethylene-bis-dithioCarbamate) compared to control while the maximum inhibition was recorded in the plates containing Rovral 50WP (Iprodion 50%), Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazole 50%), Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%), followed by Eminent Pro (Tetraconazol 12.5%+ Carbendazim 15%), with values 100%, 100%, 100% and 70.93% respectively. The moderate inhibition was recorded in PDA plate containing fungicides Cabrio Top (Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram (55%)), Bounty (Glyphosate (glycine)) and Awal 72WP (Zineb 68%+ Hexaconazole 14%) with

values of 42.78%, 44.44% and 45.46% respectively (Table 6, Figure 7) after 10 days of inoculation.

Table 6: Percent mycelial growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.025% of different fungicide(s) separately over control.

Name	Percent mycelial growth inhibition
T1= Control	-
T2= Fiesta	10.37
T3= Blitox	24.81
T4= Endofil	26.30
T5= Metaril	32.59
T6= Cabrio	42.78
T7= Bounty	44.44
T8= Awal	45.56
T9= Companion	53.89
T10= Eminent	70.93
T11= Atostin 50	100.00
T12= Rovral	100.00
T13= Contaf	100.00

Figure 7: Growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates, here, Control and containing 0.025% of A) Fiesta, B) Blitox, C) Endofil, D) Metaril, E) Cabrio, F) Bounty, G) Awal, H) Companion, I) Eminent, J) Autostin, K) Rovral and L) Contaf.

4.1.6 Effect of different fungicides at 0.05% concentration on radial mycelial growth of *Alternaria brassicicola* over control at 10 Days after Inoculation

Effect of different fungicides at 0.05% concentration on the radial mycelia growth of *A. brassicicola* were observed significant. No radial mycelia growth (cm) was recorded in plates containing Rovral 50WP (Iprodion 50%), Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazole 50%), Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%), Eminent Pro (Tetraconazol 12.5%+ Carbendazim 15%) and companion (Mancozeb 63%+Carbendazim 12%) followed by Awal 72WP (Zineb 68%+ Hexaconazole 14%) while the maximum radial mycelial growth was recorded in control plates and plates containing by Blitox 50WP (Copper oxychloride 50%) followed by Fiesta (Zinc ethylene-bis-dithio Carbamate), Metaril 72WP (Mancozeb 64%+Metalaxyl 8%), Bounty (Glyphosate (glycine)) , Indofil M45 (Mancozeb 80%) (Figure.8).

However, the medium radial mycelial growth was recorded in PDA plate containing, Cabrio Top (Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram (55%)), (Table 7, Figure 8).

Table 7: Mycelial growth of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.05% of different fungicide(s) separately over control.

Name	Mycelial Growth (cm) at 10 DAI*
T1=Control	9.00 a
T2=Blitox	8.65 b
T3=Fiesta	8.50 b
T4=Metaril	8.13 c
T5=Bounty	8.12 c
T6=Endofil	7.58 d
T7=Cabrio	3.18 e
T8=Awal	1.52 f
T9=Atostin 50	0.00 g
T10=Companion	0.00 g
T11=Contaf	0.00 g
T12=Eminent	0.00 g
T13=Rovral	0.00 g
LSD (0.05)*	0.3127

*LSD (0.05): Least Significant Difference. In a column, means followed by the same letter(s) are statistically similar at 5% level by DMRT

Figure 8: Status of radial mycelial growth of *Alternaria brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.05% of different fungicide(s) separately over control at 10 DAI (Days After Inoculation)

4.1.7 Effect of different fungicides at 0.05% on percent growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* at 10 DAI

Effect of twelve selected fungicides at 0.05% concentration on the percent growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* was also observed in this study. The result showed that there was no growth inhibition occurred on the control plate. The minimum percent growth inhibition (3.89%) was recorded in plates containing Blitox 50WP (Copper oxichloride 50%), Fiesta (Zinc ethylene-bis-dithio Carbamate) compared to control while the maximum inhibitions were recorded in the plates containing Rovral 50WP (Iprodion 50%), Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazole 50%), Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%), Eminent Pro (Tetraconazol 12.5%+ Carbendazim 15%) and Companion (Mancozeb 63%+Carbendazim 12%) followed by Awal 72WP (Zineb 68%+ Hexaconazol 14%) with values of 100%, 100%, 100% ,100%, 100% and 94.26% respectively. The moderate 64.63% inhibition was recorded in PDA plate containing Cabrio Top (Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram55%) (Table 8, Figure 9) after 10 days of inoculation.

Table 8: Percent mycelial growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.05% of different fungicide(s) separately over control.

Name	Percent mycelial growth inhibition
T1=Control	-
T2=Blitox	3.89
T3=Fiesta	5.56
T4=Metaril	9.63
T5=Bounty	9.81
T6=Endofil	15.74
T7=Cabrio	64.63
T8=Awal	94.26
T9=Atostin 50	100.00
T10=Companion	100.00
T11=Contaf	100.00
T12=Eminent	100.00
T13=Rovral	100.00

Figure 9: Growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates, here, Control and containing 0.05% of A) Blitox, B) Fiesta, C) Metaril, D) Bounty, E) Endofil, F) Cabrio, G) Awal, H) Companion, I) Eminent, J) Autostin, K) Rovral and L) Contaf.

4.1.8 Effect of different fungicides at 0.1% concentration on radial mycelial growth of *Alternaria brassicicola* over control at 10 Days after Inoculation

Effect of different fungicides at 0.1% concentration on the radial mycelia growth of *A. brassicicola* were observed significant in this study. The result revealed that there is no radial mycelia growth (cm) was recorded in plates containing Rovral 50WP (Iprodion 50%), Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazole 50%), Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%), Eminent Pro (Tetraconazol 12.5%+ Carbendazim 15%) and Companion (Mancozeb 63%+Carbendazim 12%) followed by Awal 72WP (Zineb 68%+ Hexaconazol 14%) while the maximum radial mycelial growths were recorded in control plates and plates containing by Fiesta (Zinc ethylene-bis-dithio Carbamate), Metaril 72WP (Mancozeb 64%+Metalaxyl 8%), Blitox 50WP (Copper oxichloride 50%), Indofil M45 (Mancozeb 80%) (Figure.10). However, the medium

radial mycelial growth was recorded in PDA plate containing, Cabrio Top (Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram (55%)), (Table 9, Figure 10).

Table 9: Mycelial growth of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.1% of different fungicide(s) separately over control.

Name	Mycelial Growth (cm) at 10 DAI*
T1=Control	9.00 a
T2=Fiesta	8.65 b
T3=Metaril	8.50 b
T4=Blitox	8.13 c
T5=Endofil	8.12 c
T6=Bounty	7.58 d
T7=Cabrio	3.18 e
T8=Awal	1.52 f
T9=Atostin 50	0.00 g
T10=Rovral	0.00 g
T11=Contaf	0.00 g
T12=Eminent	0.00 g
T13=Companion	0.00 g
LSD (0.05)*	0.3127

*LSD (0.05): Least Significant Difference. In a column, means followed by the same letter(s) are statistically similar at 5% level by DMRT

Figure 10: Status of radial mycelial growth of *Alternaria brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.1% of different fungicide(s) separately over control at 10 DAI (Days After Inoculation)

4.1.9 Effect of different fungicides at 0.1% on percent growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* at 10 DAI

Effect of twelve selected fungicides at 0.1% concentration on the percent growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* were also observed in this study. The result showed that there was no growth inhibition occurred on the control plate. The minimum percent growth inhibition (8.89%) was recorded in plates containing Fiesta (Zinc ethylene-bis-dithio Carbamate) compared to control while the maximum inhibition was recorded in the plates containing Rovral 50WP (Iprodion 50%), Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazole 50%), Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%), Eminent Pro (Tetraconazol 12.5%+ Carbendazim 15%) and Companion (Mancozeb 63%+Carbendazim 12%) followed by Awal 72WP (Zineb 68%+ Hexaconazole 14%) with values of 100%, 100%, 100% ,100%, 100% and 83.15% respectively. The moderate 62.96% inhibition was recorded in PDA plate containing Cabrio Top

(Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram55%) (Table 10, Figure 11) after 10 days of inoculation.

Table 10: Percent mycelial growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.1% of different fungicide(s) separately over control.

Name	Percent mycelial growth inhibition
T1=Control	-
T2=Fiesta	8.89
T3=Metaril	11.48
T4=Blitox	12.41
T5=Endofil	18.15
T6=Bounty	36.11
T7=Cabrio	62.96
T8=Awal	83.15
T9=Atostin 50	100
T10=Rovral	100
T11=Contaf	100
T12=Eminent	100
T13=Companion	100

Figure 11: Growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates, here, Control and containing 0.1% of A) Blitox, B) Fiesta, C) Metaril, D) Bounty, E) Endofil, F) Cabrio, G) Awal, H) Companion, I) Eminent, J) Autostin, K) Rovral and L) Contaf.

4.1.10 Effect of different fungicides at 0.2% concentration on radial mycelial growth of *Alternaria brassicicola* over control at 10 Days after Inoculation

Effect of different fungicides at 0.2% concentration on the radial mycelia growth of *A. brassicicola* were observed significant in this study. No radial mycelia growth (cm) was recorded in plates containing Rovral 50WP (Iprodion 50%), Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazole 50%), Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%), Eminent Pro (Tetraconazol 12.5%+Carbendazim 15%) and Companion (Mancozeb 63%+Carbendazim 12%) followed by Awal 72WP (Zineb 68%+ Hexaconazol 14%) while the maximum radial mycelial growths were recorded in control plates and plates containing by Fiesta (Zinc ethylene-bis-dithioCarbamate), Blitox 50WP (Copper oxychloride 50%), Metaril 72WP (Mancozeb 64%+Metalaxyl 8%) and Indofil M45 (Mancozeb 80%) (Figure.12). However, the medium radial mycelial growth was recorded in PDA plate containing Cabrio Top (Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram (55%)) and Bounty (Glyphosate (glycine)) (Table 11, Figure 12).

Table 11: Mycelial growth of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.2% of different fungicide(s) separately over control.

Name	Mycelial Growth (cm) at 10 DAI*
T1=Control	9.00 a
T2=Fiesta	8.20 b
T3=Blitox	7.97 bc
T4=Metaril	7.88 c
T5=Endofil	7.37 d
T6=Cabrio	5.75 e
T7=Bounty	3.33 f
T8=Auwal	1.60 g
T9=Atostin 50	0.00 h
T10=Rovral	0.00 h
T11=Contaf	0.00 h
T12=Companion	0.00 h
T13=Eminent	0.00 h
LSD(0.05)*	0.2971

***LSD (0.05):** Least Significant Difference. In a column, means followed by same letter(s) are statistically similar at 5% level by DMRT

Figure 12: Status of radial mycelial growth of *Alternaria brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.2% of different fungicide(s) separately over control at 10 DAI (Days After Inoculation)

4.1.11 Effect of different fungicides at 0.2% on percent growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* at 10 DAI

Effect of twelve selected fungicides at 0.2% concentration on the percent growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* were also observed in this study. The result showed that there was no growth inhibition occurred on the control plate. The minimum percent growth inhibition (10.37%) was recorded in plates containing Fiesta (Zinc ethylene-bis-dithio Carbamate) compared to control while the maximum inhibitions were recorded in the plates containing Rovral 50WP (Iprodion 50%), Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazole 50%), Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%), Eminent Pro (Tetraconazol 12.5%+ Carbendazim 15%) and Companion (Mancozeb 63%+Carbendazim 12%) followed by Awal 72WP (Zineb 68%+ Hexaconazol 14%) with values of 100%, 100%, 100% ,100%, 100% and 75.00% respectively. The moderate 56.67% inhibition was recorded in PDA plate containing Cabrio Top (Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram55%) (Table 12, Figure 13,) after 10 days of inoculation.

Table 12: Percent mycelial growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates containing 0.2% of different fungicide(s) separately over control.

Name	Percent mycelial growth inhibition
T1=Control	-
T2=Fiesta	10.37
T3=Blitox	14.26
T4=Metaril	22.04
T5=Endofil	22.22
T6=Cabrio	56.67
T7=Bounty	60.93
T8=Auwal	75.00
T9=Atostin 50	100
T10=Rovral	100
T11=Contaf	100
T12=Companion	100
T13=Eminent	100

Figure 13: Growth inhibition of *A. brassicicola* on PDA plates, here, Control and containing 0.2% of A) Fiesta, B) Blitox, C) Metaril, D) Endofil, E) Cabrio, F) Bounty, G) Auwal, H) Companion, I) Eminent, J) Autostin, K) Rovral and L) Contaf

4.2 Field experiment

4.2.1. Effect of fungicides on the disease incidence and severity of Alternaria leaf blight of mustard-rape seed

Effect of two selected fungicides based on their efficacy in *in vitro* experiments were evaluated for disease incidence and severity for Alternaria leaf blight of mustard. In this study Rovral 50WP (Iprodion 50%) and Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazole 50%) were sprayed at four different concentrations namely 0.0125%, 0.025%, 0.05 and 0.1% to compare the efficacy and identify the appropriate dose of most effective fungicide(s) used in this field experiment against Alternaria leaf blight disease in field condition

4.2.1.1 Incidence and severity of Alternaria leaf blight disease of mustard in single sprayed plots

The effect of different chemical treatments on diseases incidence of Alternaria leaf blight disease of mustard in single sprayed plots was summarized and shown in Table 13. In single sprayed plot fungicides were sprayed at 40 DAS and the disease incidence data were recorded at 45 and 55 DAS. However, different chemical treatments had a significant influence on percent diseases incidence of mustard at 45 and 55 DAS (Table 13). It is prominent that the percent disease incidence of Alternaria leaf blight of mustard was increased gradually with the advancement of crop growth. In this study the lowest disease incidence, 25.86% at 45 DAS and 25.4% at 55 DAS were found in T8 and T4 treatments (Rovral @ 0.1% & Contaf @ 0.1%) and the highest percent disease incidence i.e. 56.99% and 86.96% were observed in control (T0) plots at 45 and 55 DAS respectively.

On the other hand, the effect of different chemical treatments on diseases severity of Alternaria leaf blight disease of mustard in single sprayed plots was also presented in Table 13. In single sprayed plot fungicides were sprayed at 40 DAS and the disease severity data were collected at 45 and 55 DAS. However, different

chemical treatments had a significant influence on percent diseases severity of mustard at 45 and 55 DAS (Table 13). It is also visible that the percent disease severity of Alternaria leaf blight of mustard was increased gradually with the advancement of crop growth. In the present research work, the lowest disease severity 24% & 50.33% at 45 and 55 DAS respectively were found in T8 treatment (Contaf @ 0.1%) and the highest percent disease severity i.e. 57.5% and 95.68% were observed in control (T0) plots at 45 and 55 DAS respectively.

Table 13: Effect of fungicides on disease incidence and severity of Alternaria Leaf blight of mustard in Single Spray Plots

Treatments	Disease Incidence (%)				Disease severity (%)			
	Before spray	Single Spray Plot			Before spray	Single Spray Plot		
		45 DAS	55 DAS	Mean		45 DAS	55 DAS	Mean
T0 =Control	35.35cd	56.99a	86.96a	71.98	31.72a	57.5a	95.68a	76.59
T1= Rovral 0.0125%	38.46ab	34bcd	35.29bc	34.65	26b	50.17b	75.28b	62.73
T2 = Rovral 0.025%	38.46ab	33.85bcd	33.33bc	33.59	24.29bc	42c	68.32d	55.16
T3 = Rovral 0.05%	35d	32.79cd	30.65cd	31.72	20.62d	31.86d	56.71e	44.29
T4 = Rovral 0.1%	36.92bc	26.98e	25.4e	26.19	22.5cd	25.33e	52.33f	38.83
T5 = Contaf 0.0125%	39.39a	36.67b	37.93b	37.30	23.4bcd	47.14b	72.88c	60.01
T6 = Contaf 0.025%	38.3ab	36bc	34.62bc	35.31	22.66cd	41.43c	63.98d	<u>52.71</u>
T7 = Contaf 0.05%	32.35e	31.67d	31.67c	31.67	23.8bcd	30.67d	55e	42.84
T8 = Contaf 0.1%	39.29a	25.86e	25.86de	25.86	21.25cd	24e	50.33f	37.17
LSD (0.05)*	1.624	3.5165	5.0989	-	2.98	3.05	2.73	-

*LSD (0.05): Least Significant Difference. In a column, means followed by the same letter(s) are statistically similar at 5% level by DMRT.

4.2.1.2 Incidence and severity of Alternaria leaf blight disease of mustard in double spray plots

The effect of different fungicide treatments on diseases incidence of Alternaria leaf blight disease of mustard in double spray plots was summarized and shown in Table 14. In double spray, plot fungicides were sprayed at 40 and 50 DAS and the disease incidence data were recorded at 45 and 55 DAS. However, different chemical treatments had a significant influence on percent diseases incidence of mustard at 45 and 55 DAS (Table 14). It is prominent that the percent disease incidence of Alternaria leaf blight of mustard was increased gradually with the advancement of crop growth. In the present research work, the lowest percent disease incidence in the double sprayed plot (18.46%) was observed in T8 treatment (Contaf @ 0.1%), while the highest percent disease incidence (86.96%) was found in control (T0) plot (shown in table 14).

In addition, the effect of different chemical treatments on diseases severity of Alternaria leaf blight disease of mustard in double spray plots was also summarized in Table 14. In double spray, plot fungicides were sprayed at 40 and 55 DAS and the disease severity data were also collected at 45 and 55 DAS. However, different chemical treatments had a significant influence on percent diseases severity of Alternaria leaf blight of mustard at 45 and 55 DAS (see table 14). It is also distinct that the percent disease severity of Alternaria leaf blight of mustard was increased gradually with the advancement of crop growth. In the present research work, the lowest percent mean disease severity (23.11%) was found in T8 treatment (Contaf @ 0.1%) and the highest percent disease severity (95.68%) was observed in control (T0) plot in this study (Table 14).

Table 14: Effect of fungicides on disease incidence and severity of Alternaria Leaf blight of mustard in Double Spray Plots

Treatments	Disease Incidence (%)				Disease severity (%)			
	Before spray	Double Spray Plot			Before spray	Double Spray Plot		
		45 DAS	55 DAS	Mean		45 DAS	55 DAS	Mean
T0 =Control	35.35bc	56.99a	86.96a	71.98	31.72c	57.5a	95.68a	76.59
T1= Rovral 0.0125%	35.71bc	36.36b	33.93b	35.15	21.16d	52.5b	42.74b	47.62
T2 = Rovral 0.025%	34.21c	35.14b	32.43b	33.79	47.83a	40d	38.67d	39.34
T3 = Rovral 0.05%	30.65d	30cd	26.67c	28.34	38b	34e	32.33f	33.17
T4 = Rovral 0.1%	36bc	26.53d	20.41d	23.47	32.5c	28.86f	26.71g	27.79
T5 = Contaf 0.0125%	36bc	36.99b	32bc	34.50	39b	43.56c	40.28c	41.92
T6 = Contaf 0.025%	35.71bc	32.76bc	30.36bc	31.56	32.4c	39.2d9	34.33e	36.81
T7 = Contaf 0.05%	39.62a	34bc	26.53c	30.27	23.66d	35e	30.97f	32.99
T8 = Contaf 0.1%	36.51b	27.27d	18.46d	22.87	24.166d	28.57f	23.11h	25.84
LSD(0.05)*	1.86	3.92	5.16	-	3.51	2.73	1.53	-

*LSD (0.05): Least Significant Difference. In a column, means followed by the same letter(s) are statistically similar at 5% level by DMRT.

4.2.2 Effect of foliar spray of fungicides on the yield contributing parameters of mustard

Two best-performed fungicides (based on *in vitro* experiment) were used to know the effect of chemical fungicides on the yield contributing attributes of mustard in treated and control plots. The different yield contributing parameters such as the number of pods per plant, pod length, number of seeds per pod and thousand seeds weight showed significant differences in treated and control plots (Table 15).

The maximum number of pods/plant (34.5 and 61) in single and double spray plots was observed in T8 treatment (Contaf @0.1%) followed by T4 treatment (Rovral @ 0.1%), whereas the lowest number of pods/plant (8.9) was found in control plots (shown in table 15).

A positive correlation was observed between the pod length and concentration of spray fungicides. The pod length ranged from 2.5 to 4.9 cm for T0 to T8 for this study. However maximum pod length (4.6 & 4.9 cm) was also found in the plants treated with Cotaf fungicide @0.1% (T8) followed by Rovral fungicide @0.1% (T4) in single and double sprayed plots, while minimum pod length (2.5 cm) was observed in control plots.

In this study, the maximum number of seeds/ siliqua (24.2 and 26.1) was found in T8 (Contaf @0.1%) treated plants in single and double sprayed plots followed by T4 (Rovral @ 0.1%) treated plants. The lowest (14.2) number of seeds/plants were found in control plants.

To determine the effect of two selected fungicides on the weight of 1000 seeds (gm) of mustard were also evaluated in this study and this parameter showed significant differences under different treatments (Table 15). However, the weight of 1000 seeds ranged from 1.78 to 3.81 gm for T0 to T8. In case of weight of 1000 seeds, T8 (Contaf @ 0.1%) treated plants showed maximum weight (3.45 and 3.81 gm) in single and double sprayed plots followed by T4 (Rovral @ 0.1%) treated plants while the lowest (0.9gm) weight of 1000 seeds was observed in the plants belong to control plots (Table 15).

Table 15: Effect of different treatments on number of pods per plant, pod length, number of seeds per pod and thousand seeds weight of mustard at single and double spray plots

Treatments	Single Spray Plot				Double Spray Plot			
	No. of pods/Plant	Pod length (cm)	No. of seeds/silique	1000 seed weight(g)	No. of pods/Plant	Pod length (cm)	No. of seeds/silique	1000 seed weight(g)
T0 =Control	8.9d	2.5b	14.2d	0.90e	8.9f	2.5d	14.2e	0.90b
T1= Rovral 0.0125%	19.4cd	3.8a	21.2c	1.78d	10.4ef	3.2cd	21.78d	1.98ab
T2 = Rovral 0.025%	22.4bc	4.1a	21.6c	1.90cd	24d	3.5bcd	22.65cd	2.14ab
T3 = Rovral 0.05%	23.2abc	4a	22.3bc	2.40bcd	38.1b	4.6ab	23.87bc	2.76ab
T4 = Rovral 0.1%	33.4ab	4.5a	23.5ab	3.1ab	60.6a	4.5ab	25.12ab	3.43a
T5 = Contaf 0.0125%	20cd	3.8a	22.1bc	1.88cd	11e	3.6bcd	22.56cd	2.23ab
T6 = Contaf 0.025%	23.01abc	3.6ab	22.68abc	1.97cd	26c	4.2abc	24.78ab	2.98ab
T7 = Contaf 0.05%	24.2abc	4.5a	23.89ab	2.78abc	39.05b	4.6ab	25.67a	3.56a
T8 = Contaf 0.1%	34.5a	4.6a	24.25a	3.45a	61a	4.9a	26.01a	3.81a
LSD(0.05)*	10.838	1.124	1.658	0.84	1.77	1.072	1.365	1.937

*LSD (0.05): Least Significant Difference. In a column, means followed by the same letter(s) are statistically similar at 5% level by DMRT.

CHAPTER V

DISCUSSION

The present experiment had two phases namely laboratory experiment and field experiment. In the laboratory, the efficacy of twelve (12) fungicides viz Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%), Indofil M45 (Mancozeb 80%), Companion (Mancozeb 63% + Carbendazim 12%), Aqual 72WP (Zineb 68%+ Hexaconazole 14%), Blitox 50WP (Copper oxichloride 50%), Rovral 50WP (Iprodione 50%), Fiesta Z 78 (Zinc Ethylene bis-dithio Carbamate), Metaril 72 WP (Mancozeb 64%+Metalaxyl 8%), Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazol 50%), Eminent Pro (Tetraconazol 12.5%+ Carbendazim 15%), Cabrio Top {Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram (55%)} and Bounty {Glyphosate (glycine)} were evaluated against *A. brassicicola* for observing radial mycelial growth and percent growth inhibition at different concentrations till 10 Days after inoculation . The aim of the study was to identify the best fungicide(s) with appropriate dose against *A. brassicicola* pathogen. However, the results distinctly showed that Hexaconazole, Iprodione and Carbendazim containing fungicides like Contaf 5 EC, Rovral 50WP and Autostin 50WP were found highly effective in low concentration (0.0125%) i.e. they inhibited mycelial growth up to 100 percent at 0.0125% compared to other fungicides used in this study. So it was found that Hexaconazole, Iprodione and Carbendazim containing fungicides were more effective to control *A. brassicicola* compared to Mancozeb, Metalaxyl, Zineb, Pyraclostrobin, Metiram, Copper oxichloride, Zinc Ethelene bis-dithio Carbamate containing fungicides. These findings are in agreement with the findings reported by other researchers. Verma (2010) reported that three sprayings of Dithane M-45 (0.25%), Kavach (0.1%) or Foltof (0.25%) at 10 days interval significantly reduced the radial growth of the fungus in *in vitro* experiment. Mahapatra & Das (2016) reported that iprodione, propiconazole and mancozeb were effective for the control of Alternaria blight of mustard and all the three fungicides reduced the Alternaria blight disease severity in comparison to untreated control irrespective of their doses. However, hexaconazole was very effective as it caused 100% growth

inhibition in *in vitro* experiment. Kumar et al. (2017) found that in *in vitro* evaluation carbendazim containing fungicide was most effective compared to other fungicides against *Alternaria solani*. Meena et al. (2004) evaluated fungicides (Mancozeb & Carbendazim), alone or in combination for control of *Alternaria* blight (*A. Brassicae*) of Indian mustard and found that fungicides Mancozeb & Carbendazim caused 100% reduction in the mycelial growth of *A. Brassicae* over control *in vitro*.

In the field experiment, in case of single spray plots, the lowest disease incidence, (25.86% at 45 DAS and 25.4% at 55 DAS) was found in Contaf @ 0.1% and Rovral @ 0.1% treated plots and the highest percent disease incidence i.e. 56.99% and 86.96% were observed in control plots at 45 and 55 DAS respectively. In addition, the lowest disease severity (24% & 50.33% at 45 and 55 DAS respectively) was found in Contaf @ 0.1% treated plots and the highest percent disease severity i.e. 57.5% and 95.68% were observed in control plots at 45 and 55 DAS respectively. In case of double spray plots, the lowest percent disease incidence was observed in Contaf @ 0.1% treated plots and the highest percent disease incidence was found in control plots. On the other hand, the lowest percent disease severity (23.11%) was found in Contaf @ 0.1% treated plots and the highest percent disease severity (95.68%) was observed in control plots. Moreover, plots sprayed with Contaf @ 0.1% showed best performance for yield contributing parameters like number of pod per plant (61), pod length (4.9cm), number of seed per siliqua (26.01) and thousand seed weight (3.81g) followed by Rovral @ 0.1% (T4), whereas control plots showed lowest value for all yield contributing parameters in both double and single spray plots. However, these findings are also corroborates the findings of earlier researchers. Chattopadhyay and Bhunia (2003) determined the efficacy of seven fungicides against *Alternaria* leaf blight of rapeseed-mustard caused by *Alternaria brassicae*. Best control of disease was observed by Iprodione followed by Mancozeb. But maximum economic return was obtained from two spraying of mancozeb at 45 DAS and 60 DAS. Singh et al. (2008) evaluated four fungicides against *Alternaria brassicae*, causing *Alternaria* blight of mustard and that all the four fungicides were

significantly superior in reducing the disease intensity over the untreated control. Among them Iprodione was found to be the most effective fungicide in controlling the disease intensity was 11.56 (20.74) and the yield was 19.13 q/ha followed by Mancozeb, with disease intensity of 14.56 (22.24) and yield of 17.93 q/ha. The efficacy of Iprodion fungicide was found effective against *Alternaria* blight on Indian mustard and increase in yield in fungicide-treated plots compared to control (Mukhearjee *et al.*, 2003). Ayub *et al.* (1996) evaluated the efficacy of seven fungicides (*viz.* Mancozeb, Fentin hydroxide, Carbendazim, Binomil, Iprodion, Ziram and Copper saltes +Mancozeb), against *Alternaria* blight of mustard and they reported that observed all the fungicide treatment gave significant reduction in disease severity and increased seed weight and yield. Prasad *et al.* (2009) evaluated the eleven bioagents and fungicides alone and in combination with foliar spray for the management of *Alternaria* blight of mustard and found that all the treatment significantly reduced the disease severity and increased the yield over the check. They also observed combination of fungicides (Carbendazim and Ridomil MZ) was most effective to reduce the *Alternaria* blight severity. Similarly Sunder *et al* (2005) reported that the fungicide Mancozeb and Iprodion had effectively reduced *Alternaria* blight (*Alternaria brassicae*) and increase seed yield by 48% and 130% respectively. Five fungi toxicants *viz.*, mancozeb (0.2%), azoxystrobin (0.05%), propiconazole (0.05%), difenoconazole (0.05%) and hexaconazole (0.05%) were tested for their efficacy against *Alternaria* blight disease alone as single spray at 45 DAS and in combination with mancozeb at 45 DAS followed by spray of other four fungicides individually at 60 DAS under field conditions for two consecutive years during *rabi* 2015-16 and 2016-17. The spray of different fungi toxicants alone as single spray treatment or each fungicide in succession with mancozeb (0.2%) significantly reduced the *Alternaria* blight disease over control; however the level of efficacy varied among the treatments. In general, the combinations of two fungicides spray *i.e.* mancozeb at 45 DAS followed by other four fungicides each at 60 DAS have recorded lower *Alternaria* blight severity as compared to all single spray treatments. Foliar spray with mancozeb (0.2%) at 45 DAS followed by hexaconazole (0.05%) at 60 DAS was found most effective in controlling *Alternaria*

leaf blight severity up to 78.0 percent and *Alternaria* pod blight severity up to 56.5 percent and increased seed yield up to 29.9 percent as compared to untreated control.

Based on the findings of the present study it may be concluded that Hexaconazol, Iprodion and Carbendazim containing fungicides are most effective against *Alternaria brassicicola* at a very low concentration in *in vitro* condition as it inhibited radial mycelial growth up to 100% at only 0.125% concentrations. In addition, the results from the field experiment is indicating that Hexaconazole and Iprodion containing fungicide can be used @ 0.1% for the control of *Alternaria* leaf blight disease of mustard. However, Hexaconazole containing fungicides are more cheaper compared to Iprodion containing fungicides produced by different Agro-chemical producing companies in worldwide including Bangladesh and therefore, farmers may use Hexaconazole containing fungicide for controlling *Alternaria* leaf spot disease of mustard instead of Iprodion fungicide at the field level in Bangladesh.

CHAPTER VI

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Alternaria Leaf blight or black leaf spot caused by *Alternaria brassicicola* is the most notorious disease of mustard in Bangladesh and can cause a significant yield loss every year. Till to date, the chemical fungicide is still the solitary management practice at the farmers' level as none of the cultivated varieties is completely resistant against this disease. On the other hand, due to continuous and indiscriminate use of chemical fungicide, the evolution of resistant or tolerant and mutation of the virulent races of the pathogen is common in nature which makes the situation harder for the farmers to manage the disease. Hence the use of effective fungicide(s) with appropriate dose by a screening of next-generation fungicide/newly arrived single or mixed fungicides against this disease is the only viable way for the long-term control of *Alternaria* leaf blight disease of mustard in Bangladesh.

The experiments were conducted in Plant-Microbe Interaction Lab of the Department of Plant Pathology and Agronomy Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh. The Efficacy of Twelve fungicides viz. Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%), Indofil M45 (Mancozeb 80%), Companion (Mancozeb 63% + Carbendazim 12%), Awual 72WP (Zineb 68%+ Hexaconazole 14%), Blitox 50WP (Copper oxichloride 50%), Rovral 50WP (Iprodione 50%), Fiesta Z78 (Zinc Ethelene bis-dithio Carbamate), Metaril 72 WP (Mancozeb 64%+Metalaxyl 8%), Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazol 50%), Eminent Pro (Tetraconazol 12.5%+ Carbendazim 15%), Cabrio Top {Pyraclostrobin (5%) + Metiram (55%)} and Bounty {Glyphosate (glycine)} belonging to the different group were tested against *Alternaria brassicicola in vitro* to select the best effective fungicide(s) using the standard procedure of poison food technique for observing radial mycelial growth and percent growth inhibition at different concentrations till 10 days post inoculation.

The result of a lab experiment evidently showed that maximum mycelial growth inhibition (100%) of *A. brassicicola* was obtained by Hexaconazol (Contaf 5EC), Iprodion (Rovral 50 WP) and Carbendazim (Autostin 50 WP) containing fungicides at 0.0125%, 0.025%, 0.05% and 0.1% concentrations followed by Aqual (Zineb 68%+ Hexaconazol 14%). On the other hand, Blitox, Fiesta, Metaril, Bounty and Endofil were found least effective, as they inhibited only 3.89% to 18.74% of fungal mycelial growth even at 0.1% concentration.

Based on *in vitro* experiment best two fungicides namely Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazol) and Rovral 50 WP (Iprodion) were used as spray solutions to evaluate the efficacy of those fungicides against Alternaria leaf blight disease of mustard in field condition. Due to that disease incidence and severity, and some yield contributing parameters were evaluated in treated and control plots for different treatments. In this experiment, in single spray plot, the lowest disease incidence, (25.86% at 45 DAS and 25.4% at 55 DAS) was found in the plots treated with Contaf @ 0.1% and Rovral @ 0.1% and the highest percent disease incidence i.e. 56.99% and 86.96% were observed in control plots at 45 and 55 DAS respectively. In addition, single spray plots also showed the lowest disease severity 24% & 50.33% at 45 and 55 DAS respectively in Contaf @ 0.1% treated plots and the highest percent disease severity i.e. 57.5% and 95.68% were observed in control plots at 45 and 55 DAS respectively.

In the present research work, the lowest percent disease incidence in double sprayed plots (18.46%) was observed in the plots treated with Contaf @ 0.1% and the highest percent disease incidence was found in control plots. In this study, the lowest percent disease severity (23.11%) was found in the plots treated with Contaf @ 0.1% treated plots and the highest percent disease severity (95.68%) was observed in control plots in case of double spray study (Table 11).

Plots sprayed with Contaf @ 0.1% showed the best performance for yield contributing parameters like number of pod per plant (61), pod length (4.9cm), number of seed per siliqua (26.01) and thousand seed weight (3.81g) followed by Rovral @ 0.1%, whereas control plots showed the lowest value for all yield contributing parameters.

Based on the findings of the present study it may be concluded that Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazol 50%), Rovral 50WP (Iprodione 50%) and Autostin 50WP (Carbendazim 50%) were most effective under *in vitro* as it completely inhibited mycelial growth in minimum concentration (0.0125%). In addition, Contaf 5EC (Hexaconazol 50%) also performed better in the field condition as it showed the minimum percentage of disease incidence and severity and high yield contributing parameters followed by Rovral 50WP. However, it may be summarized that Contaf 5EC can be used instead of Rovral 50 EC after effective cost-benefit ratio analysis in a large-scale experiment for management of Alternaria blight of mustard in Bangladesh in the coming days.

REFERENCE

- Abd-el-Kareem F. 2007. Potassium or sodium bicarbonate in combination with Nerol for controlling early blight disease of potato plants under laboratory, greenhouse and field conditions. *Egyptian Journal of Phytopathology.*, 35(1) 73-86.
- Ahamad, S. and U. Narain, 2000. Effect of temperature, relative humidity and rainfall on development of leaf spot of bitter gourd. *Ann. Plant Prot. Sci.*, 8: 114-115.
- Ahmad A and Ashraf Y 2016. *In Vitro* and *In Vivo* Management of Alternaria Leaf Spot of Brassica campestris L. *Journal of Plant Pathology & Microbiology* 7:7.
- Aneja JK and Agnihotri A 2013. Alternaria Blight of Oilseed Brassicas: Epidemiology and Disease Control Strategies with Special Reference to Use of Biotechnological Approaches for attaining Host Resistance. *Journal of Oilseed Brassica.* 4(1): 1-10.
- Ansari NA, Kahn MW and Muheet A 1990. Evaluation of some fungicides for seed treatment and foliar application in management of damping-off of seedlings and blight of rapeseed caused by *Alternaria brassicae*. *Mycopathologia.* June 1990, Volume 110, Issue 3, pp 163-167.
- Ayub, A., Dey, R.K., Jahan, M., Ahmed, H.U. and Alam, K.B. (1996) Foliar Spray of Fungicides to Control Alternaria Blight of Mustard. *Journal of the Bangladesh Agricultural University*, 6, 47-50.
- BARC (Bangladesh Agricultural Research Council) 2012: Fertilizer Recommendation Guide. pp. 84.
- BART P. H. J. THOMMA *Alternaria* spp.: from general saprophyte to specific parasite. *Molecular Plant Pathology* (2003) 4(4), 225-236.

BBS -Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics 2015. The year book of Agricultural Statistics of Bangladesh, Ministry of Planning. Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.

Chattopadhyay A. K and Bhunia C. K. (2003).Management of *Alternaria* leaf blight of rapeseed-mustard by chemicals. *J. Mycopath. Res.* 41(2): 181-183.

Chupp C and Sherf AF 1960. Vegetable diseases and their control. Pp. 267-269. The Ronald Press Company. New York. 693 pp.

Conn KL and Tewari JP 1990. Survey of *Alternaria* blackspot and *Sclerotinia* stem rot in central Alberta in 1989. *Can. Plant Dis. Survey.* 70 66-67.

Conn KL, Tewari JP, Awasthi RP (1990). A Disease Assessment Key for *Alternaria* Black Spot in Mustard. *Can Plant Dis Sur* 70: 19-22.

Deepak kumar and Chaudhary, U. 2006. Influence of temperature on mycelium and sporulation of *A. brassicae* and *A. brassicicola* causing blight. *Journal of Research, SKUAST - J.* 5. 1: 48 - 51.

Doullah MAH, Meah MB and Okazaki K 2006. Development of an effective screening method for partial resistance to *Alternaria brassicicola* (dark leaf spot) in *Brassica rapa*. *European Journal of Plant Pathology.* 116: 33-43.

Duhan, J.C. and Suhag, L.S. 1990 *Alternaria* leaf and pod blight of cauliflower. *Indian Phytopathology.*, 43(3): 231-234.

Evans KJ, Nyquist WE & Latin RX. 1992. A Model Based on Temperature and Leaf Wetness Duration for Establishment of *Alternaria* Leaf Blight of Muskmelon *Phytopathology*, 82(8), 890-895.

Gangawane L V1997. Management of fungicide resistance in Plant Pathogen. *Indian Phytopathology* 50 : 305-313.

Gomez KA and Gomez AA 1984: *Statistical Procedures for Agricultural Research*. 2nd Edn. John Willey and Sons., New York. pp. 97-111.

Gondal AS, Ijaz M, Riaz K and Khan AR 2012. Effect of Different Doses of Fungicide (Mancozeb) against *Alternaria* Leaf Blight of Tomato in Tunnel. Journal of Plant Pathology & Microbiology 3:3.

http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/jspui/bitstream/10603/167534/10/10_chapter%202.pdf

Humpherson-Jones FM 1989. Survival of *Alternaria brassicae* and *Alternaria brassicicola* on crop debris of oilseed rape and cabbage. Ann. appl. Biol. 115 45-50.

ISTA 1996: International rules for Seed Testing. Seed Science and Technology. 4: 3-49.

Jones R K 2000. Assessment of FHB of wheat and barley in respect to fungicide treatment. Plant Disease 84 : 1021-1030. .

Kadian AK and Saharan GS. 1983. Symptomatology, host range and assessment of yield losses due to *Alternaria brassicae* infection in rapeseed and mustard. Indian J. Mycol. Pl. Pathol. (13): 319-323.

Kadian AK and Saharan GS. 1983. Symptomatology, host range and assessment of yield losses due to *Alternaria brassicae* infection in rapeseed and mustard. Indian J. Mycol. Pl. Pathol. (13): 319-323.

Katiyar A., Kant S., Chauhan S.S. and Alka S. (2001) Ann. Plant Protec. Sci., 9(2), 339-341.

Khan MM, Khan RU and Mohiddin FA 2007. Studies on the cost-effective management of *Alternaria* blight of rapeseed-mustard (*Brassica* spp.). **Phytopathol. Mediterr. (46) 201-206.**

King SR 1994. Screening, selection and genetics of resistance to *Alternaria* diseases in *Brassica oleracea*. Ph.D.thesis, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York.

Kolte SJ (1985) Diseases of Annual Edible Oilseed Crops, Vol. II, Rapeseed- Mustard and Sesame Diseases. CRC Press Inc. Boca Raton, Florida p: 135.

- Kolte SJ 2002. Diseases and their management in oilseed crops, new paradigm in oilseeds and oils: research and development needs. Indian Society of Oilseeds Research 244-252.
- Kumar V, Gurvinder S and Tyagi A 2017. Evaluation of Different Fungicides against Alternaria Leaf Blight of Tomato (*Alternaria solani*). International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences 6(5): 2343-2350.
- Mahapatra S and Das S 2016. Evaluation of fungicides against alternaria leaf blight of mustard. Indian Journal of Plant Protection 44:1 99-103.
- Maude, R.B., and F.M. Humpherson-Jones. 1980a. Studies on the seed-borne phases of dark leaf spot (*Alternaria brassicicola*) and grey leaf spot (*Alternaria brassicae*) of brassicas. Ann. appl. Biol. 95:331-319.
- Meah M.B. and Hossain I 1988. Screening of germplasm of oilseeds against some diseases and their chemical control. Proc.BAU Res. Sys. Workshop.pp: 52-59.
- Meena P. D., Meena R. L., Chattopadhyay, C. and Kumar, A. (2004). Identification of critical stage for disease development and biocontrol of alternaria blight of Indian mustard (*B. juncea*). *J.Phytopath.* 152 (4): 204-209.
- Mukharjee I, Gopal M and Chatterjee SC. 2003. Persistence and effectiveness of Ipodion against A. blight in mustard. Bulletin of environment contamination and toxicology. 70 (3): 586-591.
- Nene Y.L. and P.N. Thapliyal, 1993. Fungicides in Plant Disease Control. Oxford and IBH Publishing Co., New Delhi, New Delhi, India 579 pp.
- Nowicki M, Nowakowska M, Niezgodna A and Kozik E. 2012. Alternaria black spot of crucifers: symptoms, importance of disease, and perspectives of resistance breeding. Vegetable Crops Research Bulletin vol. 76, 5-19. (DOI: 10.2478/v10032-012-0001-6)
- Pandey, M.K., Ved, Ratan and Singh, Jyoti. 2002. Effect of different temperatures and hydrogen - iron concentrations on the growth and sporulation of *Alternaria lini*

- (L.) causing leaf blight in linseed. Indian journal of Plant Pathology .20 (1&2): 70-71.
- Patil, M.J., Ukey, SP and Raut, BT. 2003. Evaluation of fungicides and botanicals for the management of early blight (*Alternaria solani*) of tomato. Punjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth Res. J., 25 (1): 49-51.
- Paul VH, Rawlinson CJ (1992) Diseases and Pests of Rape. Gelsenkirchen- Buer, Germany: Verlag Th. Mann.
- Prasad Rajendra, Maurya KK, Srivastava SBL. 2009. Ecofriendly management of *A.* blight of Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea* L). Journal of seeds Research. 26 (1):65.
- Prasad Y and Naik MK 2003. Evaluation of genotypes, fungicides and plant extracts against early blight of tomato caused by *Alternaria solani*. Indian J. Plant Protec. 31(2): 49-53.
- Rotem J 1994. The Genus *Alternaria*: biology, epidemiology and pathogenicity. American Phytopathological Society Press, St Paul, MN.
- Sadana D and Didwania N 2015. Bioefficacy of Fungicides and Plant Extracts against *Alternaria solani* Causing Early Blight of Tomato. International Conference on Plant, Marine and Environmental Sciences (PMES-2015) Jan. 1-2.
- Sangeetha, C .G. and Siddaramaiah, A. L. 2007. Epidemiological studies of white rust, downy mildew and *Alternaria* blight of Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea* Linn.) Czern.andCoss.). African Journal of Agricultural Research Vol. 2 (7), 305-308.
- Sidlauskiene A, Rasinskiene A and Surviliene E. 2003. Effect of various protection means on *Alternaria* diseases of tomato, cucumber and cabbage seed plants. Sodininkyste-ir-Darzininkyste., 22(3): 388-394.
- Singh A. 2008. Efficacy of new fungicides in the management of early and late blight of potato. Indian Phytopathology 61(1): 134-135.

- Singh K and Rai M. 2003. Evaluation of chemicals against *Alternaria* leaf spot of brinjal. Ann. Plant Protec. Sci., 11(2): 394-395.
- Singh PC and Singh D. 2006. *In vitro* evaluation of fungicides against *Alternaria alternata*. Ann. Plant Protec. Sci., 14(2): 500-502.
- Singh R.B. and R.N. Singh, 2005. Fungicidal management of foliar diseases of mustard in mid-eastern India. Indian Phytopathology 58, 51-56.
- Singh V, Shrivastava A, Jadon S., Wahi N, Singh A and Sharma N. 2015. *Alternaria* diseases of vegetable crops and its management control to reduce the low production. 7(13) 843-840.
- Sinha PP and Prasad RK. 1989. Chemical management of *Alternaria* blight of cauliflower seed crop. Ind. J. Mycol. Plant Pathol. 19: 204-205.
- Sultana NA, Khan MAH, Islam MN and Nahar K 2009. Evaluation of Appropriate Time for the Application of Rovral against *Alternaria* Blight Incidence and Yield of Mustard. International Journal of Sustainable Agriculture 1 (1): 20-23.
- Sunder *et al.* (2005) screened the mustard cultivars against *Alternaria brassicae* and found that cultivars Krishna and Pusa bold were less Susceptible than Varuna.
- Valkonen, J.P.T. and Koponen, H. (1990) The Seed-Borne Fungi of Chinese Cabbage (*Brassica pekinensis*), Their Pathogenicity and Control. Plant Pathology, 39, 510-516.
- Verma N and Verma S. 2010. *Alternaria* diseases of vegetable crops and new approaches for its control. Asian J. Exp. Biol. Sci., 1(3): 681-692.
- Verma P R and Saharan G S. (1994). Monograph on alternaria diseases of Crucifers Sakatoon, SK, Canada: Saskatoon Research Centre technical Bulletin 1994-6E, Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada.

REFERENCE

- Abd-el-Kareem F. 2007. Potassium or sodium bicarbonate in combination with Nerol for controlling early blight disease of potato plants under laboratory, greenhouse and field conditions. *Egyptian Journal of Phytopathology.*, 35(1) 73-86.
- Ahamad, S. and U. Narain, 2000. Effect of temperature, relative humidity and rainfall on development of leaf spot of bitter gourd. *Ann. Plant Prot. Sci.*, 8: 114-115.
- Ahmad A and Ashraf Y 2016. *In Vitro* and *In Vivo* Management of Alternaria Leaf Spot of Brassica campestris L. *Journal of Plant Pathology & Microbiology* 7:7.
- Aneja JK and Agnihotri A 2013. Alternaria Blight of Oilseed Brassicas: Epidemiology and Disease Control Strategies with Special Reference to Use of Biotechnological Approaches for attaining Host Resistance. *Journal of Oilseed Brassica.* 4(1): 1-10.
- Ansari NA, Kahn MW and Muheet A 1990. Evaluation of some fungicides for seed treatment and foliar application in management of damping-off of seedlings and blight of rapeseed caused by *Alternaria brassicae*. *Mycopathologia.* June 1990, Volume 110, Issue 3, pp 163–167.
- Ayub, A., Dey, R.K., Jahan, M., Ahmed, H.U. and Alam, K.B. (1996) Foliar Spray of Fungicides to Control Alternaria Blight of Mustard. *Journal of the Bangladesh Agricultural University*, 6, 47-50.
- BARC (Bangladesh Agricultural Research Council) 2012: Fertilizer Recommendation Guide. pp. 84.
- BART P. H. J. THOMMA *Alternaria* spp.: from general saprophyte to specific parasite. *Molecular Plant Pathology* (2003) 4(4), 225–236.
- BBS -Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics 2015. The year book of Agricultural Statistics of Bangladesh, Ministry of Planning. Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.

- Chattopadhyay A. K and Bhunia C. K. (2003). Management of *Alternaria* leaf blight of rapeseed-mustard by chemicals. *J. Mycopath. Res.* 41(2): 181-183.
- Chupp C and Sherf AF 1960. Vegetable diseases and their control. Pp. 267-269. The Ronald Press Company. New York. 693 pp.
- Conn KL and Tewari JP 1990. Survey of *Alternaria* blackspot and *Sclerotinia* stem rot in central Alberta in 1989. *Can. Plant Dis. Survey.* 70 66-67.
- Conn KL, Tewari JP, Awasthi RP (1990). A Disease Assessment Key for *Alternaria* Black Spot in Mustard. *Can Plant Dis Sur* 70: 19-22.
- Deepak kumar and Chaudhary, U. 2006. Influence of temperature on mycelium and sporulation of *A. brassicae* and *A. brassicicola* causing blight. *Journal of Research, SKUAST - J.* 5. 1: 48 - 51.
- Doullah MAH, Meah MB and Okazaki K 2006. Development of an effective screening method for partial resistance to *Alternaria brassicicola* (dark leaf spot) in *Brassica rapa*. *European Journal of Plant Pathology.* 116: 33-43.
- Dubey RC, Kumar H and Pandey PR 2009: fungitoxic effect of neem extracts on growth and sclerotial survival of *Macrophomina phaseolina* *in vitro*. *Journal of American Science.* 5: 17-24.
- Duhan, J.C. and Suhag, L.S. 1990 *Alternaria* leaf and pod blight of cauliflower. *Indian Phytopathology.*, 43(3): 231-234.
- Evans KJ, Nyquist WE & Latin RX. 1992. A Model Based on Temperature and Leaf Wetness Duration for Establishment of *Alternaria* Leaf Blight of Muskmelon *Phytopathology*, 82(8), 890-895.
- Gangawane L V 1997. Management of fungicide resistance in Plant Pathogen. *Indian Phytopathology* 50 : 305-313.
- Gomez KA and Gomez AA 1984: *Statistical Procedures for Agricultural Research*. 2nd Edn. John Willey and Sons., New York. pp. 97-111.

Gondal AS, Ijaz M, Riaz K and Khan AR 2012. Effect of Different Doses of Fungicide (Mancozeb) against *Alternaria* Leaf Blight of Tomato in Tunnel. Journal of Plant Pathology & Microbiology 3:3.

http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/jspui/bitstream/10603/167534/10/10_chapter%202.pdf

Humpherson-Jones FM 1989. Survival of *Alternaria brassicae* and *Alternaria brassicicola* on crop debris of oilseed rape and cabbage. Ann. appl. Biol. 115 45-50.

ISTA 1996: International rules for Seed Testing. Seed Science and Technology. 4: 3-49.

Jones R K 2000. Assessment of FHB of wheat and barley in respect to fungicide treatment. Plant Disease 84 : 1021-1030. .

Kadian AK and Saharan GS. 1983. Symptomatology, host range and assessment of yield losses due to *Alternaria brassicae* infection in rapeseed and mustard. Indian J. Mycol. Pl. Pathol. (13): 319-323.

Kadian AK and Saharan GS. 1983. Symptomatology, host range and assessment of yield losses due to *Alternaria brassicae* infection in rapeseed and mustard. Indian J. Mycol. Pl. Pathol. (13): 319-323.

Katiyar A., Kant S., Chauhan S.S. and Alka S. (2001) Ann. Plant Protec. Sci., 9(2), 339-341.

Khan MM, Khan RU and Mohiddin FA 2007. Studies on the cost-effective management of *Alternaria* blight of rapeseed-mustard (*Brassica* spp.). Phytopathol. Mediterr. (46) 201-206.

King SR 1994. Screening, selection and genetics of resistance to *Alternaria* diseases in *Brassica oleracea*. Ph.D.thesis, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York.

Kolte SJ (1985) Diseases of Annual Edible Oilseed Crops, Vol. II, Rapeseed- Mustard and Sesame Diseases. CRC Press Inc. Boca Raton, Florida p: 135.

- Kolte SJ 2002. Diseases and their management in oilseed crops, new paradigm in oilseeds and oils: research and development needs. Indian Society of Oilseeds Research 244-252.
- Kumar V, Gurvinder S and Tyagi A 2017. Evaluation of Different Fungicides against Alternaria Leaf Blight of Tomato (*Alternaria solani*). International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences 6(5): 2343-2350.
- Mahapatra S and Das S 2016. Evaluation of fungicides against alternaria leaf blight of mustard. Indian Journal of Plant Protection 44:1 99-103.
- Maude, R.B., and F.M. Humpherson-Jones. 1980a. Studies on the seed-borne phases of dark leaf spot (*Alternaria brassicicola*) and grey leaf spot (*Alternaria brassicae*) of brassicas. Ann. appl. Biol. 95:331-319.
- Meah M.B. and Hossain I 1988. Screening of germplasm of oilseeds against some diseases and their chemical control. Proc.BAU Res. Sys. Workshop.pp: 52-59.
- Meena P. D., Meena R. L., Chattopadhyay, C. and Kumar, A. (2004). Identification of critical stage for disease development and biocontrol of alternaria blight of Indian mustard (*B. juncea*). J.Phytopath. 152 (4): 204-209.
- Mukharjee I, Gopal M and Chatterjee SC. 2003. Persistence and effectiveness of Ipodion against A. blight in mustard. Bulletin of environment contamination and toxicology. 70 (3): 586-591.
- Nene Y.L. and P.N. Thapliyal, 1993. Fungicides in Plant Disease Control. Oxford and IBH Publishing Co., New Delhi, New Delhi, India 579 pp.
- Nowicki M, Nowakowska M, Niezgoda A and Kozik E. 2012. Alternaria black spot of crucifers: symptoms, importance of disease, and perspectives of resistance breeding. Vegetable Crops Research Bulletin vol. 76, 5-19. (DOI: 10.2478/v10032-012-0001-6)
- Pandey, M.K., Ved, Ratan and Singh, Jyoti. 2002. Effect of different temperatures and hydrogen - iron concentrations on the growth and sporulation of *Alternaria lini*

- (L.) causing leaf blight in linseed. Indian journal of Plant Pathology .20 (1&2): 70-71.
- Patil, M.J., Ukey, SP and Raut, BT. 2003. Evaluation of fungicides and botanicals for the management of early blight (*Alternaria solani*) of tomato. Punjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth Res. J., 25 (1): 49-51.
- Paul VH, Rawlinson CJ (1992) Diseases and Pests of Rape. Gelsenkirchen- Buer, Germany: Verlag Th. Mann.
- Prasad Rajendra, Maurya KK, Srivastava SBL. 2009. Ecofriendly management of *A.* blight of Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea L.*). Journal of seeds Research. 26 (1):65.
- Prasad Y and Naik MK 2003. Evaluation of genotypes, fungicides and plant extracts against early blight of tomato caused by *Alternaria solani*. Indian J. Plant Protec. 31(2): 49-53.
- Rotem J 1994. The Genus *Alternaria*: biology, epidemiology and pathogenicity. American Phytopathological Society Press, St Paul, MN.
- Sadana D and Didwania N 2015. Bioefficacy of Fungicides and Plant Extracts against *Alternaria solani* Causing Early Blight of Tomato. International Conference on Plant, Marine and Environmental Sciences (PMES-2015) Jan. 1-2.
- Sangeetha, C .G. and Siddaramaiah, A. L. 2007. Epidemiological studies of white rust, downy mildew and *Alternaria* blight of Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea Linn.*) Czern.andCoss.). African Journal of Agricultural Research Vol. 2 (7), 305-308.
- Satish S, Mohana DC, Ranhavendra MP and Raveesha KA 2007: Antifungal activity of some plant extracts against important seed borne pathogens of *Aspergillus spp.* Journal of Agriculture Technology 3(1): 109-119.
- Sidlauskiene A, Rasinskiene A and Surviliene E. 2003. Effect of various protection means on *Alternaria* diseases of tomato, cucumber and cabbage seed plants. Sodininkyste-ir-Darzininkyste., 22(3): 388-394.

- Singh A. 2008. Efficacy of new fungicides in the management of early and late blight of potato. *Indian Phytopathology* 61(1): 134-135.
- Singh K and Rai M. 2003. Evaluation of chemicals against *Alternaria* leaf spot of brinjal. *Ann. Plant Protec. Sci.*, 11(2): 394-395.
- Singh PC and Singh D. 2006. *In vitro* evaluation of fungicides against *Alternaria alternata*. *Ann. Plant Protec. Sci.*, 14(2): 500-502.
- Singh R.B. and R.N. Singh, 2005. Fungicidal management of foliar diseases of mustard in mid-eastern India. *Indian Phytopathology* 58, 51-56.
- Singh V, Shrivastava A, Jadon S., Wahi N, Singh A and Sharma N. 2015. *Alternaria* diseases of vegetable crops and its management control to reduce the low production. 7(13) 843-840.
- Sinha PP and Prasad RK. 1989. Chemical management of *Alternaria* blight of cauliflower seed crop. *Ind. J. Mycol. Plant Pathol.* 19: 204-205.
- Sultana NA, Khan MAH, Islam MN and Nahar K 2009. Evaluation of Appropriate Time for the Application of Rovral against *Alternaria* Blight Incidence and Yield of Mustard. *International Journal of Sustainable Agriculture* 1 (1): 20-23.
- Sunder *et al.* (2005) screened the mustard cultivars against *Alternaria brassicae* and found that cultivars Krishna and Pusa bold were less Susceptible than Varuna.
- Valkonen, J.P.T. and Koponen, H. (1990) The Seed-Borne Fungi of Chinese Cabbage (*Brassica pekinensis*), Their Pathogenicity and Control. *Plant Pathology*, 39, 510-516.
- Verma N and Verma S. 2010. *Alternaria* diseases of vegetable crops and new approaches for its control. *Asian J. Exp. Biol. Sci.*, 1(3): 681-692.
- Verma P R and Saharan G S. (1994). Monograph on alternaria diseases of Crucifers Sakatoon, SK, Canada: Saskatoon Research Centre technical Bulletin 1994-6E, Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada.